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NURSES' ADHERENCE TO A NURSE-DRIVEN CAUTI PREVENTION PROTOCOL

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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ABSTRACT

Catheter-associated urinary tract infections (CAUTI) are the most frequent healthcare-acquired infections and account for up to 80% of all these infections. Evidence supports that the development of a standardized and systematic approach to CAUTI prevention using a bundle of interventions to supplement a nurse-driven protocol is effective in reducing indwelling urinary catheter (IUC) utilization rates, and days. The purpose of this DNP project was to decrease IUC utilization rates and IUC days in the Intensive Care Unit (ICU) by improving nurses' adherence to a nurse-driven CAUTI prevention protocol. The project was an evidence-based improvement project which included a survey, observations, and audits. The project setting was an ICU, in a non-profit acute care hospital. The project had a convenience sample of 47 frontline registered nurses and a consecutive sample of 138 patients with Foley catheter. This project was conducted in two phases, pre and post implementation. The pre-implementation phase included an 11-item nurses' survey used to identify barriers to nurses' adherence to the nurse-driven CAUTI prevention protocol. Post-implementation included a 10-item and seven-item checklists respectively used to conduct daily ICUs rounding and electronic chart reviews. Additionally, a manual IUC removal reminder was used. On day one of IUC insertion or an IUC patient admission, a standardized evidence-based educational handout was used to perform patient/family education on proper IUC maintenance and CAUTI risks. Pre- and post-implementation protocol adherence rates, IUC days and IUC utilization rates were evaluated and compared. A Chi-squared, Fisher exact, and Poisson exact tests were conducted to determine if there were statistically significant changes in the post-implementation findings when compared to the pre-implementation results. Most commonly reported barriers to nurses' adherence to the CAUTI prevention protocol included heavy nursing load (72.7% of respondents), fear of spending more time charting (70%), lack of timely physician order for Foley catheter removal (59.1%), and lack of time (56.8%). Post-implementation, there was a statistically significant increase in nurses' adherence to the overall CAUTI prevention protocol (55.3%, $p < 0.001$) from 40.8 to 96.1%. Unadjusted, IUC days seemed to have decreased post-implementation from 519 to 406. However, when adjusted with patient days, there was no statistically significant change between the pre- and post-implementation IUC utilization rates (816.04 vs 816.90/1000 catheter days, $p = 1.000$). Supplementing a bundle of activities to an evidence-based nurse-driven protocol improved nurses' adherence to the CAUTI prevention protocol even though IUC utilization rates did not decrease. Exogenous factors (Covid-19 pandemic surge) appeared to be a threat that negatively impacted the project findings. Providing a clear pathway for nurse driven IUC removal along with an ongoing CAUTI prevention protocol, and adherence monitoring is essential to ensure that safe practices are fully embedded in IUC patient care and sustained. Continuous evaluation and monitoring of barriers to CAUTI prevention protocols are crucial to decrease IUC use and improve IUC care in hospital settings.

Keywords: adherence to a nurse-driven CAUTI prevention protocol, adherence rate, chart review, chart review checklist, catheter associated urinary tract infection prevention (CAUTI),

CAUTI prevention, daily rounding, daily rounding checklist, Foley catheter, Nurse-driven protocol, nurse-driven protocol for CAUTI prevention, nurse-driven protocol for Foley catheter removal.

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Background

Problem

Catheter-associated urinary tract infections (CAUTI) are the most frequent healthcare-acquired infections and account for up to 80% of all hospital-acquired infections (Connor, 2017). An indwelling urinary catheter (IUC) that has been left in too long or has become contaminated can cause a CAUTI. An IUC is a tube placed through the urethra, which drains urine from the bladder. In the United States, there are an estimated 449,334 CAUTI events (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), 2019). A CAUTI is associated with increased length of stay (LOS), morbidity, mortality, and increased overall healthcare costs (CDC, 2019; Connor, 2017). Moreover, a CAUTI is a reportable event (CDC, 2019). Additionally, the Center for Medicare and Medicaid Services (CMS) does not reimburse CAUTI care related costs (Peasah, McKay, Harman, Al-Amin, & Cook, 2013). There is a positive correlation between the risk of CAUTI and the duration of catheterization. Each day an IUC is in place, there is a 3% to 7% chance of a CAUTI occurrence (CDC, 2019; Gould et al., 2009).

The onset of a CAUTI creates significant and avoidable patient discomfort, pain, distress, embarrassment, and activity restrictions, along with a substantial care burden for the hospital (CDC, 2019). Catheter acquired UTIs are also associated with clinical complications such as sepsis (Gould, 2017), prostatitis, epididymitis, orchitis in males, cystitis, pyelonephritis, gram-negative bacteremia, endocarditis, vertebral osteomyelitis, septic arthritis, endophthalmitis, and meningitis (CDC, 2019). These complications may also lead to increased mortality. Moreover, CAUTIs are responsible for 13,000 deaths each year (CDC, 2019). The cost of a CAUTI is estimated to be \$758, with a total of \$340 million spent annually by hospitals in related costs

(CDC, 2019). The management of an IUC is critical in eliminating CAUTI events and preventing further healthcare complications.

Significance

A large urban hospital reported an unacceptable number of CAUTI events with high catheter utilization rates and catheter days. In 2020, the hospital accounted for five CAUTI events, with four in the ICU alone (Juliet Nussbaum, internal data, January 4, 2021).

Furthermore, one new case of CAUTI was identified in the ICU in January 2021. The total number of catheter days in 2020 was 6,677 with 3,922 days for non-ICUs and 2,755 days for ICU patients, ICU holding the highest number of days for any single unit. A focused review of the new cases revealed that nurses' non-compliance with the established protocol was the primary reason for the increase in CAUTIs (Juliet Nussbaum, internal data, January 4, 2021).

The problem this project addresses is the need to identify and address the barriers to the CAUTI prevention protocol adherence by nurses.

The hospital nurse-driven urinary catheter and bladder management clinical policy and protocol's (CAUTI prevention protocol) objective is to ensure the health and safety of patients using evidence-based practice and national guidelines to manage IUCs and to reduce unnecessary urinary catheterization. According to this protocol, IUCs shall be inserted only when indicated and removed as soon as possible to prevent CAUTIs. A licensed independent practitioner (LIP) order is required to insert an IUC. A licensed independent practitioner is an individual, as permitted by law and regulation, and by the organization, to provide care and services without direction or supervision within the scope of the individual's license and consistent with the privileges granted by the organization (Juliet Nussbaum, communication, January 4, 2021).

When there is a LIP's order for a IUC insertion, the nurse must first determine if there is a need for an IUC or another non-invasive alternative method for draining the bladder. If the nurse determines that an IUC is needed, she shall then insert it using aseptic techniques and place the patient on a monitoring schedule. During monitoring, the patient's IUC shall be managed using the hospital's evidence-based guideline and protocol (Appendix A). The patient shall be continually assessed each shift for the necessity of the IUC. Once the nurse determines that the IUC is no longer needed (if the patient does not meet criteria for maintaining an IUC and there is no continuation order) the registered nurse must remove the IUC immediately per the hospital's policy and protocol guidelines. The registered nurse shall educate the patient/family on the indications for IUC and risks, the insertion, maintenance, and removal procedures, and the necessity for timely removal of IUCs. IUC indication, insertion, maintenance and removal, and patient/family education guidelines are included in the hospital urinary catheter and bladder management clinical policy, procedure, and protocol (see Appendix A).

Purpose

The purpose of this DNP project was to decrease Foley catheter utilization rates and catheter days in the Intensive Care Unit (ICU) by improving nurses' adherence to a nurse-driven CAUTI prevention protocol at a not-for-profit acute care hospital. The objectives were to:

- Collect baseline data on Foley catheter utilization rates, Foley catheter days, and protocol adherence rates.
- Identify barriers to nurses' adherence to the protocol.
- Develop and pilot a bundle of activities to supplement the protocol and improve adherence rates.

- Evaluate nurse's adherence to the protocol and bundle of activities as well as post-implementation Foley catheter utilization rates and catheter days.

A literature review was conducted to identify factors that contribute to poor adherence to protocols. Based on the literature findings, a bundle of evidence-based interventions was developed with the goal to increase nurses' adherence to the nurse-driven protocol. Nurse's improvement in knowledge and their intention to follow the nurse-driven protocol were measured as part of the project. The desired long-term goal of this project was to have a sustainable reduction in the overall hospital CAUTI events and rates.

Supporting Framework: Iowa Model of Evidence-Based Practice

Applying evidence-based practice (EBP) is a significant challenge for nurses implementing changes (Nielson, 2015). A theoretical framework assists in identifying key factors and processes used to facilitate the implementation of EBPs (Nielson, 2015). It serves as an organized structure that provides a step-by-step pattern of reasoning that guides the development of evidence-based investigations (Nielson, 2015). Such a model can then assist researchers in placing their findings within the context of science. The project was organized and conducted using the 2015 revised version of the Iowa Model of Evidence-Based Practice (the Iowa Model) (Appendix B). The Iowa Model is a framework used as a guide for the implementation of evidence-based practice interventions (Iowa Model Collaborative et al., 2017). Numerous healthcare settings, professionals, and academic institutions have used the Iowa Model to organize and conduct research studies that improved clinical practices and outcomes (Brown, 2014; Doody & Doody, 2011; Lloyd et al., 2016). The Iowa Model consists of seven steps:

- 1) Identify trigger issues

- 2) State the purpose
- 3) Form a team
- 4) Evaluate and synthesize the research regarding the topic of study
- 5) Design and pilot a practice change
- 6) Integrate and sustain the practice change
- 7) Disseminate the post-implementation results (Iowa Model Collaborative et al., 2017).

The integration of the Iowa Model into the present project began with the first two steps, which are to identify triggering issues for improvement and to state what the purpose is (Iowa Model Collaborative et al., 2017). The triggering issue for this project was the increased CAUTI events that were the result of the nursing staff's non-compliance to the CAUTI prevention protocol. The 2020 baseline data highlighted five CAUTI events associated with high catheter utilization rates and catheter days. The purpose of the project was to decrease IUCs utilization rates and IUC days by improving frontline RNs' adherence to the nurse-driven CAUTI prevention protocol. The CAUTI prevention project was a priority at the project hospital, as the current CAUTI events were associated with low patient-satisfaction, poor clinical outcomes, lower reimbursements, and increased hospital costs. The third step of the Iowa Model is to form a team (Iowa Model Collaborative et al., 2017). For the purpose of the project, an interdisciplinary team comprised of the ICU Director, the infection prevention preventionist, four charge nurses (two day and two night shift), three CAUTI champions, and the project author. The interdisciplinary team ensured that the project was comprehensive and multifaceted and allowed for brainstorming, forming, and implementing the CAUTI prevention project. The fourth step was to gather, appraise, and summarize the evidence (Iowa Model Collaborative et al.,

2017). A literature review was conducted using OVID, SCOPUS, Pubmed, CINAHL, Cochrane, and Google scholar databases.

The fifth step was to design and pilot the practice change (Iowa Model Collaborative et al., 2017). Since sufficient evidence was gathered from the initial literature review, the practice change design was initiated. The practice design was completed in 4 phases. Phase One involved the evaluation of the use of the CAUTI prevention protocol by nurses through a survey designed to uncover barriers leading to protocol non-adherence. A SWOT analysis was used to evaluate the environment as well. Phase two of the practice design was to create a bundle of interventions supplementing the current CAUTI prevention protocol. The bundle of interventions was tailored to address the barriers identified by the nurses from the survey conducted in the first phase, and to promote nurses' adherence to the CAUTI prevention protocol. Phase three of the practice change design targeted the adoption of this new bundle interventions by nurses. Finally, phase four of the practice change design included the collection and reporting of post-implementation baseline data.

After implementation of the practice change, step six of the Iowa Model drove the integration and sustainment of the change (Iowa Model Collaborative et al., 2017). The latter step involved the engagement of three frontline nurses designated as project champions, as well as monitoring of adherence rates, Foley catheter utilization rate, Foley catheter days, and CAUTI events by the Quality Improvement department. As key indicators were being monitored, step seven involved the dissemination of follow-up IUC utilization rates, IUC days, and CAUTI events throughout the organization. Using the Iowa Model, the project steps were presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1*Iowa Model of Evidence-Based Practice*

The aim of this section was to provide an overview of the project background, significance, purpose, and theoretical framework. CAUTIs are the most frequent hospital acquired UTIs (Connor, 2017). They are associated with poor clinical outcomes and increased healthcare costs (CDC, 2019). Despite the implementation of a CAUTI prevention protocol, the project facility was having recurrent CAUTI events. The proposed intervention of this project focused on increasing nurses' adherence to the current CAUTI prevention protocol and decreasing Foley catheter utilization rates and catheter days. The Iowa Model was used as the supporting framework for this Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) evidence-based (EB) improvement project. The seven steps of the model guided the project implementation process. To examine the best evidence for CAUTI prevention, the project author conducted a literature review.

Review of Literature

The continuous improvement of healthcare services mainly focuses on ensuring positive clinical outcomes while lowering costs. Due to the lack of reimbursement for hospital-acquired infections (HAIs), healthcare institutions and regulatory agencies have begun to monitor these events. Catheter acquired urinary tract infections are the leading cause of HAIs (CDC, 2019). The CDC defines a CAUTI as an infection associated with a urinary catheter that involves the urethra, bladder, ureters, or kidneys (CDC, 2019). The CMS, CDC, American Nurses Association (ANA), and other healthcare regulatory institutions have developed evidence-based guidelines that aim to decrease the occurrence of CAUTIs.

Despite the implementation of guidelines and protocols, there are more than 560, 000 CAUTI events per year (AHRQ, 2015; CDC, 2017; ANA, 2017). This DNP project aimed to identify factors influencing nurses' adherence to protocols and to select the best evidence to supplement a CAUTI prevention protocol, as well as to decrease Foley catheter utilization rates and Foley catheter days at the project facility's ICU. The review of literature was organized into five sections:

- Plan of the literature search
- Associations Between Nurses' Adherence to Protocols and Clinical outcomes
- Factors associated with adherence to protocols and guidelines
- Evidence-based bundles of interventions to improve nurses' adherence
- Patient and family education

Plan for Literature Search

The literature review involved the exploration of five databases and one website which were: OVID, SCOPUS, Pubmed, CINAHL, Cochrane, and Google scholar. An initial search was

performed using the key terms, “Indwelling urinary catheter,” “Foley catheter,” “UTI,” “CAUTI,” “CAUTI prevention,” “policy,” “protocol,” “guidelines,” “practice change,” “compliance,” “adherence,” “Compliance to protocols,” “adherence to protocols,” “adherence to guidelines,” “Compliance to guidelines,” “adherence to policy,” “compliance to policy,” “barriers,” “barriers to protocol adherence,” “barriers to guidelines adherence,” “barriers to policy adherence,” “barriers to compliance.”

This search yielded 1563 articles. Inclusion and exclusion criteria were applied to reflect the project’s purpose and to obtain the latest research on the topic. Inclusion criteria consisted of studies in acute care settings, interventions related to CAUTI prevention, adherence/compliance to protocols/guidelines /policies by nurses, and studies published in English within the last thirteen years. Exclusion criteria included studies with a broad focus-examining adherence to items other than protocols/guidelines, non-acute hospital settings, studies completed before 2007, non-nurse driven protocols, non-CAUTI prevention protocols, non-CAUTI prevention interventions, or bundle of interventions. Application of the inclusion and exclusion criteria within the initial article search yielded 10 articles: one meta-analysis, one randomized control study, two retrospective studies, two observational studies, one prospective study, two quasi-experimental studies, and one undefined design. The selected 10 articles are discussed within their various research topics.

Relationship Between Nurses’ Adherence to Protocols and Clinical Outcomes

The CDC, ANA, CMS, AHRQ, and other healthcare organizations have established EBP CAUTI prevention guidelines addressing insertion criteria, timely removal of catheters, and maintenance. Furthermore, national quality organizations such as AHRQ have not only assembled EBP guidelines but also provided implementation pathways, checklists, educational

information, and other tools to support healthcare institutions in their efforts to address challenges associated with CAUTI rates. Healthcare institutions have integrated these guidelines into their CAUTI prevention process and have utilized them to create evidence based CAUTI prevention protocols and algorithms. Guidelines are “a set of recommendations, involving both the evidence and value judgments regarding benefits and harms of alternative care options, addressing how patients with a specific condition should be managed, everything else being equal” (Shekelle, 2018, Overview section).

Protocols are “sets of predetermined criteria that define appropriate nursing interventions and describe situations in which the nurse makes judgments relative to a course of action for effective management of common patient problems.” (HIM-HIPAA Insider, 2015, para. 3). Although both clinical guidelines and protocols aim to provide healthcare practitioners with the best evidence for clinical interventions, they display some differences. The difference being that clinical guidelines are EB recommendations; while protocols are EB methods, interventions, and policies that a healthcare professional should follow. Although several authors have used the terms interchangeably (Okraïnec et al., 2017; Francke et al., 2008; Prost & Nelson, 2016), the word protocol will be used throughout this DNP proposal.

Nursing adherence to protocols is the extent to which nurses follow the instructions they have been given in the protocols (Chapman, 2018). For this DNP project, adherence was represented by a checkmark on all the items listed on the rounding/audit checklist. Several studies have identified patient outcomes associated with nurse adherence to protocols. The most frequently cited outcomes across these studies are CAUTI rates, CAUTI events, catheter utilization rates, and catheter days. (Major-Joynes, Pegues, & Bradway, 2016; Okraïnec et al., 2017; Prost & Nelson, 2016; Quinn, 2015; Al-Hameed, 2018). Nurses’ adherence to protocols

was also found to be associated with decreased hospital length of stay (Okraínec et al., 2017; Prost and Nelson 2008), higher patient survival rates, and decreased care costs (Prost & Nelson, 2016).

Okraínec et al. (2017) conducted a prospective study that aimed to assess nurses' adherence to a Foley catheter removal protocol called Enhanced Recovery After Surgery (ERAS), to determine whether nurses' adherence to ERAS was correlated to positive CAUTI outcomes in post-operative gastrointestinal patients. The protocol mandated that post rectal and colonic surgery Foley catheters be removed at 24 hours or before 72 hours, depending on the type of surgery performed. Results demonstrated that nurses' adherence to clinical guidelines/protocol leads to a decrease in catheter days, CAUTI events, and decreased hospital length of stay. Following colonic and rectal surgeries, patients with compliant nurses had significantly fewer CAUTIs than patients with non-compliant nurses (0.8 percent compared to 4.1 percent; RR 0.20, 95% CI 0.07-0.58; P = 0.003). The result was similar in rectal surgery. Only 3.5 percent of patients with compliant nurses had a CAUTI versus 9.6 percent for those with non-compliant nurses (RR, 0.37, 95% CI 0.20- 0.68; P = 0.001). The median hospital length of stay for colonic and rectal surgeries was also significantly shorter for patients with compliant nurses versus those with non-compliant nurses: four versus five days in colonic procedures (RR 0.54, 95% CI 0.49-0.59; P = 0.001), and five versus eight days in rectal surgery (RR 0.54, 95% CI 0.49-0.59; P = 0.001).

Similarly, Prost and Nelson (2007) identified a positive association between increased nursing compliance to protocols and increased ICU patient survival rates, as well as decreased healthcare costs. In this research, intrinsic reward strategies were used to increase nurses' compliance with the protocols, leading to lower ICU mortality rates and reduced costs. The

results of the study of Okrainec et al. (2017) were statistically significant (low RRs and CIs, and P values), valid and reliable (large sample N = 2927, the rigor of its methods, study conducted in 15 hospitals for over 2.5 years). One of its few limitations was that the authors did not identify the reason why nurses were non-compliant. Some Foley catheters may have been kept in longer for valid reasons (examples: complications and patient monitoring). Plost and Nelson's (2007) study had some limitations as well, including a small convenience sample size (N = 9 protocols). However, these limitations did not alter the overall rigor and quality of the two studies.

Factors Associated with Adherence to Protocols

Several studies commonly concluded that nurses' adherence to protocols had been associated with staff empowerment, improved clinical outcomes, and lowered costs (Okrainec et al., 2017; Plost & Nelson, 2007). However, nurses and other healthcare practitioners do not systematically follow recommendations prescribed in protocols and clinical guidelines (Francke et al., 2008). Factors that influence adherence to protocols have been explored in the literature (Francke et al., 2008). Al-Hameed (2018) examined the factors that positively affected adherence to protocols/guidelines while Francke et al. (2008) looked to identify barriers to adherence to guidelines/protocols.

Al-Hameed et al. (2018) concluded that nurses' adherence to a CAUTI prevention protocol and activities bundle increased when standard CAUTI prevention education was provided to nurses, alternatives to Foley catheters were available along with ongoing Foley catheter removal reminders. In this study, an increase in nurses' adherence led to a decrease in Foley catheter days (from 2.3 in 2010 to 0.3 in 2016) and CAUTI rates (from 2.3/100 catheter days in 2010 to 0.1-0.2/100 catheter days in 2016). Al-Hameed et al. explored positive factors associated with adherence to protocols while Francke et al. (2008) sought to understand the

barriers that affected adherence to guidelines through a meta-analysis. The results identified five barriers:

- Characteristics of the guidelines (high complexity/difficultly understanding the protocol may decrease the degree of compliance)
- Characteristics of the implementation strategies (combined strategies, use of a bundle of interventions, comprehensiveness of the strategy which influence implementation)
- Characteristics of the professionals (lack of awareness, limited familiarity, lack of agreement with the guidelines, health professional's experience)
- Characteristics of the environment (limited time, personal resources and work pressure, negative attitude, and limited peers/superiors support)
- Characteristics of patients (the patient's perception of the need for guidelines can promote or create patient's resistance toward the application of guidelines)

The authors concluded that multiple strategies are needed to enhance the implementation of guidelines.

Despite Al-Hameed's study limitations (sample size and baseline compliance rate not specified), the results were sustained results from 2010 to 2011, with continued positive results in 2016. Francke et al.'s study was published in 2008, but it continues to be relevant given its design (meta-analysis) and methods rigor. Furthermore, meta-analyses are the highest level of evidence. Al-Hameed et al. (2018) and Francke et al. (2008) studies supplement each other since the first one explored the factors that positively affected compliance to protocols while the second study identified barriers to protocols.

Bundle of Interventions to Increase Nurses' Adherence

The availability and dissemination of EB protocols are not always effective in changing clinical practice. The literature suggests that incorporation of activity bundles leads to greater adherence to protocols than a single approach (Tyson et al., 2018; Theobald et al., 2017; Regagnin et al., 2016). Several of the cited studies showed that, when coupled with an EB protocol, approaches such as bedside rounding, chart reviews/audits, and use of Foley catheter removal reminders were associated with improved nurses' adherence leading to improved clinical outcomes and decreased costs.

Bedside Rounding

Tyson et al. (2018) and Pulvis et al. (2007) commonly used bedside team rounding to increase nurses' adherence to a nurse-driven protocol or a checklist to decrease Foley utilization rate and CAUTI rate. In their retrospective cohort study, Tyson et al. (2018) implemented a multimodal CAUTI prevention bundle to decrease Foley catheter utilization and decrease CAUTI rates. The researchers supplemented a twice-a-day CAUTI rounding with an audit checklist to a nurse-driven CAUTI prevention protocol for early Foley catheter removal. During the rounding, each Foley catheter patient was assessed for the continued need of the catheter, with nurses being asked to remove the Foley catheter if deemed inappropriate. Bedside rounding promoted nurse adherence to the protocol, which led to decreased Foley catheter utilization rate from 0.78 to 0.70 ($P = 0.05$), and decreased CAUTI rate from 5.1/1000 to 2.0/1000 catheter days (IRR 0.38, 95% CI 0.21-0.65). Despite its small sample ($N = 59$), this study has a high level of validity and reliability.

In contrast to the study by Tyson et al. (2018) in which the authors utilized a bundle of activities, Pulvis et al. (2007) used a single intervention. In this study, the researchers instituted

daily leadership rounding called CAUTI rounds. The CAUTI rounds were conducted for 30 minutes on every unit, including the ICU. The rounding team included the unit manager, the project sponsors (Associate Chief Medical Officer and Associate Chief Nursing Officer), the Clinical Nurse Specialist, the attending staff nurse, and any other available multidisciplinary team member. A rounding checklist was used to monitor nurse compliance with the completion of items identified in the checklist (catheter utilization indication, insertion, duration). The CAUTI rounding were found to be successful in maintaining nurse adherence to the Foley catheter management checklist. Nurses' adherence led to a decrease in catheter utilization rate from 1.8 to 0.13. There was also a decrease in CAUTI events from 86 to 30, and in CAUTI rate from 3.1 to 1.4. Compared to Tyson et al. (2018) study, this research was less effective. In the study by Tyson et al. (2018), CAUTI rate decreased from 5.1/1000 to 2.0/1000 catheter days while in the research by Purvis et al. (2017), the CAUTI rate decreased from 3.1 to 1.4/1000 catheter days only. This difference may have been correlated to the number of interventions used; the first study implemented a bundle of interventions, while the second one utilized a single intervention approach. A limitation of the study by Purvis et al. (2017) was that the sample size was not specified.

Chart Reviews and Audits

In their pre- and post-interventional quasi-experimental study, Regagnin et al. (2016) bundled monthly audits in the ICUs and SDUs, the use of a Foley catheter insertion team, and the utilization of a CAUTI prevention nurse. Monthly audits were performed on random patients with Foley catheters using an audit checklist. Audits were conducted to monitor nurses' adherence to the items in the Foley catheter insertion aseptic techniques in the checklist. Catheter days decreased and CAUTI rates fell from 7.0 to 0.9/catheter days in the ICUs. In the SDUs,

CAUTI rates decreased from 14.9 to 6.6/1000 catheter days (all $P < 0.001$). This study was strengthened by its sustainability since the study was conducted over nine years. A limitation was that the sample size was not specified.

The observational pre-post intervention study by Giles et al. (2015) similarly selected a two modal bundle consisting of the use of a Foley catheter management protocol combined with audits. During the implementation phase, a compliance audit sheet was developed to reflect the care bundle and was used by the CAUTI champions to conduct a daily audit over a two-week period. Champions also ensured ongoing nurses were compliant, which ensured the sustainability of the project. In the post-implementation phase, chart audits were performed over three months to evaluate nurse adherence with the care bundle. As in the study by Regagnin et al. (2016), the intervention bundle was found effective in promoting adherence to the care bundle. Overall, the CAUTI rate decreased to 2.2 %.

Foley Catheter Removal Reminders

Foley catheter removal reminders, regardless of the type, have shown to be effective in increasing nurses' compliance to timely IUC removal (Mitchell et al., 2019; and Theobald et al., 2017). In a randomized stepped-wedge trial, Mitchell et al. (2019) sought to evaluate the effectiveness of an electronic reminder device (CATH TAG) used to promote nurses' adherence to CAUTI prevention measures to reduce IUC duration and CAUTI rates. A CATH TAG was applied to the IUC to prompt the removal of the IUC. The device flashed a red light every 24 hours to remind nurses that they should reassess the need for the IUC. The study concluded that the use of CATH TAG was effective in increasing nurses' compliance with timely IUCs removal, which reduced Foley catheter duration and CAUTI rates on Med/Surg floors (23%). Results were not found to be significant in the ICU. This may have been due to the high acuity of ICU with

more critically sick patients. They may have required the use of Foley Catheters for a longer period of time, ultimately leading to an increase of Foley catheter days and risk of UTIs. This study had a large sample size and used a mixed-methods approach, which increased the rigor of its methods.

Similarly, Theobald et al. (2017) implemented a multifaceted intervention that involved a bedside catheter reminder, electronic 48-hour stop orders for Foley catheter removal, a structured IUC physician order within the EMR, the multidisciplinary team education, and the use of a post-IUC care protocol. The bedside reminder required the nurse of the IUC patient to write down the HIPAA compliant mnemonic “DINC” (Do I Need a Catheter?) on the patient’s room board. The mnemonic reminded physicians, attending nurses and other multidisciplinary team members to reassess the need for continuation of the IUC. An automated “Stop-Orders” was activated once the physician had put in the order for a Foley catheter. The “Stop-Orders” required that the need for the Foley catheter be reviewed every 48 hours after placement until the Foley catheter was removed. Compared to the study by Mitchell et al., (2019), this research was more effective. The use of both types of reminders increased the healthcare team’s compliance with timely IUC removal. This study also reported a significant reduction in IUC utilization rates, IUC days, and CAUTI rates (from 3.53/1000 IUC days to 0.70/1000 IUC days); and increased proper Foley catheter use resulting in an increase in the average number of days without a CAUTI. These positive results were not associated with any adverse increase in falls or ICU reinsertion (balancing measures). This study had a high level of validity and reliability.

Standardized Patient and Family Education

In their 2008 meta-analysis, Francke et al. (2008) sought to understand the barriers that affected adherence to protocols. The authors identified five barriers to nurses' adherence to

protocols, including the patient's perception of the protocol. They concluded that the patient's perception of the need for protocols either promotes patient adherence to protocols or creates a patient's resistance toward the application of protocols by nurses. Similarly, the CDC (2019) had underlined that the knowledge of Foley catheter risks, Foley catheter indications, and CAUTI prevention strategies promote patient and family adherence to Foley catheter management guidelines and decrease patient/family resistance toward the application of protocols by nurses. The CDC had created an EB patient/family CAUTI prevention handout that had proven to increase patient/family knowledge of CAUTI prevention strategies and promote patient-centered care (CDC, 2019). The handout describes a urinary catheter and a CAUTI, identifies the causes of a CAUTI, presents the symptoms of a CAUTI, common strategies used by hospitals and patients to prevent CAUTIs, and post-hospitalization considerations (CDC, 2019). The handout is available on the CDC website.

Summary

This review of the literature highlighted the available evidence regarding successful CAUTI prevention initiatives. The literature review provided evidence that implementing a single intervention approach may not be as effective as the utilization of a bundle of interventions. Of the 10 studies analyzed, only two had a single intervention approach (Michell et al., 2019; Purvis et al., 2017). One study that implemented a single intervention (bedside rounding) was less effective compared to another one that used a bundle of activities approach (bedside rounding and use of a Foley catheter removal protocol) (Purvis et al., 2017; Tyson et al., 2018). Activities that increased nurses' adherence to protocols and guidelines included bundles such as Foley catheter removal reminders, bedside rounding, and audits. A large majority of the studies used the same measures (compliance rate, CAUTI rate, Foley catheter utilization rate,

Foley catheter days). Only one of them was not effective in decreasing CAUTI rates in the ICU even though its interventions were effective in the SDUs (Mitchell et al., 2019). Francke et al. (2008), as well as the CDC (2019), underline the importance of patient and family compliance and education on the application of protocols by nurses. Most of the studies held a high degree of validity and reliability due to their design, large sample, and the rigor of their methods and analysis. The most common limitation identified was related to the sample size that was not specified in some studies.

Overall, results showed that the development of a standardized and systematic approach to CAUTI prevention using a bundle of interventions is effective in reducing CAUTI rates, catheter utilization rates, and catheter days by providing a clear EB pathway for nurse initiated IUC management. Ongoing monitoring of nurses' adherence to CAUTI protocols is essential to ensuring sustained positive change. Nurses' adherence to monitoring requires that barriers to compliance be identified and addressed. This DNP project aimed to assess and address the compliance gap in the nurse driven CAUTI prevention protocol at the project facility. The project author developed a multifaceted bundle of interventions that capitalized on the barriers (barriers identified by the project facility staff as well as barriers analyzed in the literature) and activity bundles discussed in this literature review.

Methods

The purpose of this DNP project was to reduce the utilization and duration of Foley catheters in the Intensive Care Unit (ICU) by improving nurses' adherence to a nurse-driven CAUTI prevention protocol. Catheter acquired urinary tract infections can be avoided by implementing evidence-based interventions (AHRQ, 2015). Nurses' adherence to CAUTI prevention protocols had shown to be successful in decreasing CAUTI rates (Tyson et al., 2018). The literature review demonstrated that non-compliance to CAUTI protocols negatively affects clinical outcomes. The project objectives consisted of:

- Collecting baseline data on Foley catheter utilization rate, catheter days.
- Identifying barriers to nurses' adherence to the protocol.
- Developing and piloting a bundle of activities to supplement the protocol and improve adherence rates.
- Evaluating nurses' adherence to the protocol and bundle of activities as well as evaluate post-implementation Foley catheter utilization rates and catheter days.

This section described the project's design, setting, stakeholders, sample, ethical considerations, procedures, measures, data collection, data analysis and evaluation, monitoring and sustainability, and timeline.

Design and Setting

This DNP project was an evidence-based improvement project. The project setting is a 334-bed not-for-profit acute care hospital located in Los Angeles. It is a stroke and S-T Elevated Myocardial Infarction (STEMI) federally approved center that offers a full range of services, including heart and vascular, colorectal surgery, breast cancer, emergency, orthopedic and spine care, family and maternity, burn, behavioral, and transplant care services. The facility receives

approximately 40,000 inpatients, 667,000 outpatients, and an average of 125,000 patients in the emergency department per year. The ICU was selected to pilot the project because most ICU's patients require the use of a Foley catheter at some point during their hospital stay. The ICU is a 25-bed unit that delivers advanced care and monitoring services to patients with life-threatening illnesses and injuries. The ICU is composed of two wards with 47 RNs working at the bedside.

Stakeholders

The project's stakeholders included physicians/nurse practitioners (including intensivists), infection prevention nurse, and hospital leaders (ICU Director, ICU charge nurses, Education Director, Chief Nursing officer), information management and technology team (IT team), and central supply service. Stakeholders assisted in ensuring that the project moves forward by providing their support.

Sample

This project included a convenience sample of ICU RNs and a consecutive sample of ICU patients. The first sample consisted of all 47 ICU RNs, including all full time, part-time, per diem, and traveler nurses who spoke and read English. Non-RNs, RNs who did not read and speak English, agency RNs, and RNs who worked in the ICU sporadically, coming from other units within the hospital were excluded. The second sample included all patients admitted in the ICU from January 1, 2021 to January 30, 2021(N = 73) (pre-implementation phase), and from January 31, 2021 to March 1, 2021(N = 65) (implementation phase). Inclusion criteria was ICU patients with an IUC. Exclusion criteria included non-ICU patients, ICU patients without a Foley catheter, and those with a non-indwelling catheter. Non-indwelling catheters are suprapubic catheters, condom catheters, and "In and out" catheterization (CDC, 2019).

Ethical Considerations

The project was approved by the Institutional Research Board (IRB) of the California State University, Los Angeles (Appendix C). The IRB determined that the project was exempt from further review. This approval was based on the minimal risk to human subjects.

Informed Consent

An informational letter was provided to all frontline staff prior to their participation in the nurses' survey (Appendix D). The informational letter aimed to describe the purpose of the survey, the participation time, nature of the information requested, the benefits and risks of participating, and how the information collected will be used and safeguarded. The informational letter also served as informed consent when the participants read it and completed the survey. There was no coercion. Participation was anonymous and voluntary. Participants were informed that they could withdraw at any time without penalty.

Confidentiality

Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act (HIPAA) and privacy requirements were followed to protect patients' health information. All surveys were anonymously completed to ensure the protection of participant identities and possible coercion from the employer. This project did not utilize protected health information as all data were aggregated and deidentified. All surveys were kept in a locked cabinet in the Infection Prevention Service's office and were accessible only to the infection preventionist and the project author. All electronic data were stored in a secured device and required a secure password for retrieval. Surveys will be destroyed with a paper shredder and electronic data deleted three years after the study completion.

Procedures

This section discussed the formation of the project team, the pre-intervention meeting/education, communication with staff, pre-intervention evaluation, and the pilot bundle of interventions.

Identification of CAUTI Champions

Three frontline RNs that had demonstrated strong infection prevention skills/knowledge and understanding of CAUTI prevention concepts, safety culture, and quality improvement were selected as CAUTI champions. The CAUTI champions served as early adopters who motivated frontline nurses to be engaged and active in the unit based CAUTI prevention project activities. The CAUTI champions promoted teamwork and good communication in the unit through education and coaching of frontline nurses.

Formation of the Project Team

The interdisciplinary team comprised of an infection prevention nurse, the ICU director, four charge nurses (day and night shift), three CAUTI champions, and the project author. The interdisciplinary team held weekly meetings to assess problems and evaluate the project's progress. The interdisciplinary team developed a weekly report based upon the weekly project activity, which was shared with staff nurses during their huddles. This report was also shared with the ICU director and the chief nursing officer (CNO). The chief nursing officer and central service coordinator assured the availability of resources such as house-wide communication and alternatives for Foley catheter (bladder scans, urinals, bedpans, condoms, catheters, women's external catheters / PureWick).

Pre-Intervention Meeting/Education

The project author provided a half-hour preliminary CAUTI prevention education session to the interdisciplinary team. The purpose of the education session was to review the CAUTI prevention protocol, the daily rounding checklist (Appendix E), and chart review tools (Appendix F) as well as to clarify team members' roles. The infection preventionist coordinated the preliminary education session.

Communication with ICU Staff

The project team communicated with the ICU staff to ensure that there is buy-in of the project. After the multidisciplinary project team formation, the ICU Director and the project author briefed the ICU staff on the purpose and process of the CAUTI prevention project during the multidisciplinary rounding. Three educational posters were displayed on the wall by the ICU entrance and in the staff lounge room. The posters presented information about CAUTI prevention to motivate and educate the staff. The first poster (Appendix G) was a presentation on IUC's risks and indications. The second (Appendix H) displayed information about EB CAUTI prevention practices (IUC insertion, proper use, maintenance, and prompt removal). The third poster (Appendix I) motivated ICU staff to consider using alternatives to Foley catheters. These posters were educational materials obtained from the AHRQ website.

Pre-Intervention Evaluation

A SWOT (Strengths-Weaknesses-Opportunities-Threats) analysis was conducted in January 2021 to evaluate the environment, staff readiness, and potential barriers to CAUTI prevention protocol adherence. The SWOT analysis (Appendix J) was conducted using a 30-minute brainstorming session by the multidisciplinary project team. In addition, a hard copy-survey was distributed in January 2021 to frontline RNs to evaluate their perceptions of potential

barriers to adherence to the protocol (Appendix K). The SWOT and surveys analysis, as well as the literature, helped to identify and address barriers to nurses' adherence to the CAUTI prevention protocol. Results were communicated to the ICU director, the infection prevention nurse, the director of education, and the CNO.

Pilot Bundle of Interventions

The implementation of the pilot bundle of interventions spanned from January 31, 2021, to March 1, 2021. The following EB interventions were used:

- Daily bedside rounding and audits for patients with Foley catheters
- daily electronic medical record (EMR) chart reviews
- Foley catheter removal reminder
- Standardization of patient and family education

Daily Bedside Rounding

Daily rounding and audits (DR) were completed by the attending unit's charge nurse and the attending RN for patients with a urinary catheter in place. The DRs were completed during the daily multidisciplinary rounding. The purpose of the DTRs was to observe if all the daily maintenance activities identified in the protocol were completed and to assess the necessity of IUC continuation. Upon determination that there was no indication for an IUC, the IUC order was discontinued and the IUC was removed by the attending RN. The project author created a daily rounding checklist that was used for the DTRs (Appendix E). The rounding checklist reflected the IUC management items on the CAUTI prevention protocol.

Weekly Chart Reviews

The infection preventionist completed a daily EMR chart review of all patients with IUC. The purpose of the chart review was to assess if Foley catheter insertions, indications,

removals, and all the daily maintenance activities identified in the protocol were documented in the EMR as completed by attending nurses. A chart review checklist designed by the project author was used (Appendix F). Data were collected and recorded onto an Excel spreadsheet created by the project author. The spreadsheet was stored in the hospital's database. The project author was provided with related aggregated data.

Foley Catheter Removal Reminder

A manual written Foley catheter removal reminder system was implemented. The project author designed and printed reusable laminated cards with the acronym "DINC" ("Do I Need a Foley Catheter?"). The reminder was placed on the patient's exterior glass door after a Foley catheter was inserted. The written reminder was used to cue attending nurses, charge nurses, or any multidisciplinary team member to reassess the need for catheterization and to discontinue the catheter if it did not meet the indication for continued use. Additionally, the reminder helped in mandating the ordering physicians to either discontinue the Foley catheter order or to reassess the need for the Foley catheter, requiring the renewal of the Foley catheter order only if necessary. Charge nurses and the project author briefed nurses during the shift huddle about the reminders. The CNO communicated the new intervention to physicians via a memo and email.

Standardized Patient and Family Education

The 2019 CDC's patient/family CAUTI prevention handout was used. The educational handout described a CAUTI, a urinary catheter, identifies the causes of a CAUTI, presents the symptoms of a CAUTI, common strategies used by hospitals and patients to prevent CAUTIs, and the post-hospitalization considerations (CDC, 2019). Within 24 hours of Foley catheter insertion, the attending nurse provided a competent patient with the educational handout (most patients were sedated, intubated, or unconscious. Family was not allowed to visit patients due to

the Covid-19 pandemic). Nurses will also use the handout for patient education on CAUTI prevention. The handout is available on the CDC website (Appendix C).

Measures

A CAUTI is defined as a urinary tract infection that occurs when the Foley has been in place for at least two days with a fever over 38 degrees Celsius and a positive urinary culture of more than five to ten colony forming units (CFU) (AHRA, 2015). The identification of outcome indicators is a critical step in an evidenced-based project. The measures for this project were derived from the overall project purpose and goal. It was important to monitor the progress made through data surveillance to measure the success of the pilot intervention.

Outcome variables included Foley catheter utilization rate, Foley catheter days, and protocol adherence rate. The Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality (AHRQ, 2015) formulas for catheter utilization rate and catheter days were used. All outcome variables were collected over a period of one month for both pre-intervention and post-intervention. The following calculations were conducted on the outcome variables:

- Foley catheter utilization rate is the total catheter days (numerator) divided by the total patient days (denominator) multiplied by 100 (AHRQ, 2015).
- Catheter days represent the number of days all urinary catheters were used. Total patient-days is the total number of days patients were in the unit (AHRQ, 2015).
- Protocol adherence rate is the total number of patients with IUCs for whom the nursing staff initiated, fully completed, and documented the Foley catheter management bundle in the EMR and the protocol (numerator) divided by the total number of patients with Foley catheters (denominator). The standardization factor of the adherence rate was multiplied by 100 for expression as a percentage.

Adherence was represented by a checkmark of ‘Yes’ on all the items listed on the rounding/chart review checklists. Urinary catheter management documentation involves the initiation of the Foley catheter management bundle in the EMR.

Regarding Foley catheter management, the facility’s current CAUTI prevention protocol included the following items:

- The documentation of:
 - Daily indication for Foley catheter use
 - Assessment of the continued need for Foley catheter
- The completion and documentation of:
 - Daily perineal care
 - Daily Foley catheter care (properly secured catheter, Foley catheter drainage bag below the bladder level, Foley catheter not touching the floor, no kink /unobstructed urine flow, sterile closed drainage system, Foley catheter bag no more than 2/3 full, urine assessment (output amount and character), and type and size of the catheter)
 - Provision of CAUTI prevention education to the patient/family within 24 hours of Foley catheter insertion

The Foley catheter management documentation items were completed by the attending RN every shift for all patients with a Foley catheter.

Data Collection

Data collection were performed through chart reviews and daily rounding audits. Charge nurses and CAUTI prevention champions collected bedside rounding audit data while the infection preventionist performed weekly chart reviews. Foley catheter utilization rates and

catheter day baseline data covered the period between January to December 2020. Pre-implementation and implementation bedside rounding and chart reviews data collection were performed respectively from January 1, 2021 to January 30, 2021, and from January 31, 2021 to March 1, 2021. The infection preventionist provided the baseline, pre-intervention, and ongoing intervention data (Foley catheter days, Foley catheter utilization rates, and adherence rates). The infection preventionist also assisted in reviewing possible CAUTI cases to identify CAUTI events and their root-causes.

Data Analysis and Evaluation

Data analysis was performed using the IBM Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) Statistics, version 27 for Windows, and R version 4.0.3. A pre-intervention 11 question nurses' survey was distributed and analyzed. Pre- and post-intervention data related to Foley catheter utilization rates, catheter days, and nurses' adherence to the CAUTI prevention protocol were assessed and compared to evaluate the success of the pilot interventions. Findings were communicated to the stakeholders including associated recommendations for future practices and identifying limitations.

Nurses' Survey

Information obtained from the nurses' survey included:

- Barriers to proper documentation
- Barriers to aseptic Foley catheter insertions
- Barriers to EB Foley catheter maintenance, and
- Barriers to timely Foley catheter removal

This survey was composed of five categories of questions. Questions 1 to 5 were on a 5-point Likert scale that helped to capture the respondents' opinions and perceptions of barriers to

CAUTI prevention protocol adherence. A Likert scale is a survey rating system that aims to measure participants' perceptions, opinions, or attitudes by enabling them to select from a series of choices rating their degree of agreement ("Strongly agree," "agree," "Neutral," "Disagree," "Strongly disagree"). Questions six to 10 were multiple-choice checklist items. They had two categorical answers (yes or no) depending on whether the box is checked or not. There was no order to these two specific categories. Question 11 was related to participants' demographics. It included age, gender, level of education, licenses and certifications earned, length of work experience within the facility, and in the ICU. The five-point Likert scale questions, multiple choice, age, gender, and level of education were summarized using descriptive statistics, primarily frequency tables. The length of time participants worked in the ICU and in the facility were made into ratio variables since participants' responses were in years. Summary statistics (mean, standard deviation, median, minimum, and maximum) were used to summarize these variables. No statistical comparisons were conducted on the nurses' survey, since it was completed only one time, during the pre-implementation phase. Data were presented in the form of tables.

Daily Rounding and Chart Reviews

Both daily roundings and electronic chart reviews were performed pre- and post-implementation. Between seven and twenty-four foley catheters were audited daily. Pre- and post-implementation data were collected using a daily rounding checklist (10 yes/no items) and a chart review checklist (seven yes/no items).

Daily rounding checklist items included:

- Item 1: The indwelling urinary catheter used for an appropriate indication
- Item 2: Necessity for continuing the indwelling urinary catheter assessed

- Item 3: Seal between the catheter and collecting tubing intact
- Item 4: Catheter tubing unobstructed and not twisted, kinked, or looped
- Item 5: Urine collection bag below the level of the bladder
- Item 6: Catheter secured on the patient leg
- Item 7: Catheter not touching the floor
- Item 8: Catheter bag no more than 2/3 full
- Item 9: Daily perineal care completed
- Item 10: Patient &/or family provided with education handout within 24 hours of IUC insertion

Chart review checklist included:

- Item 1: Indwelling urinary catheter insertion/start documented (Started in MediTech)
- Item 2: Indwelling urinary catheter used for an appropriate indication
- Item 3: Necessity for continuing the indwelling urinary catheter documented
- Item 4: Daily perineal care documented
- Item 5: Urine assessment documented (output and character)
- Item 6: Urinary catheter assessment documented (type & size)
- Item 7: Patient and/or family education documented

All items were first considered individually (to assess the compliance rates for individual items), then globally (to evaluate the compliance rates of all daily rounding items, chart review items, and the protocol). For a given checklist, the protocol was followed if all items were checked “Yes” (completed). The percentage of each checklist item that was checked as “completed” or “Yes” was calculated. Pre- and post-intervention findings were compared. Tables and run charts were used to show how the post-implementation daily rounding and chart review

checklist item compliance changed over the four weeks of post-intervention data collection. This was done by creating a new nominal item that was “yes” if all items of each checklist were checked, and “no” if not, and by calculating the percentage of “yes” and “no.”

The same process was followed when evaluating overall nurse’s adherence to the CAUTI prevention protocol. For one specific IUC, a nurse was compliant to the protocol if all items were checked “Yes” on both daily rounding and chart review checklist combined. The overall full compliance with all the CAUTI prevention protocol items (compliance with all daily rounding checklist items and all chart review checklist items combined) was evaluated. In order to compare pre-implementation and post-intervention data and to determine whether a likely random chance could have produced the changes, a Chi-squared and a Fisher exact test statistical analysis were performed. Both of these tests were designed to compare nominal items or percentages across two or more independent groups (Kim, 2017). The Chi-squared test required three statistics which include the Pearson chi-square (χ^2), the degrees of freedom (df), and the *p*-value. The degrees of freedom are related to the number of comparisons that were conducted (Kim, 2017), which in this case was just one. In some cases, a Fisher exact test was used instead of a chi-square test because it was more appropriate than the Chi-square test when the numbers in the table were small (Kim, 2017). In this project, a comparison of the percentages of yes/no responses from the pre-implementation checklists with the percentages of yes/no responses for the post-implementation checklists was performed. In addition to the review of data on nurses’ adherence to the CAUTI prevention protocol, Foley catheter days and Foley catheter utilization rates were examined.

Foley Catheter Utilization Rates and Foley Catheter Days

Pre- and post-implementation Foley catheter days and Foley catheter utilization rates data were analyzed and compared to evaluate the effectiveness of the pilot bundle of interventions. Pre- and post-intervention catheter days and patient days were provided weekly. Run charts were used to monitor pre- and post-implementation variables. In order to determine whether there was a statistically significant difference between the pre-implementation and post-implementation IUC days and IUC utilization rates, the Poisson Exact test was used. This test was appropriate for comparing counts, particularly when adjusting by an “offset” (like patient days) to compare rates. Since the Poisson exact test cannot be performed in base SPSS, the analysis was performed using R version 4.0.3. Results were presented using tables, run charts, and graphs.

Monitoring and Sustainability

Monitoring and planning the sustainability of the project are crucial to maintain the projected positive outcomes. Maintenance of CAUTI champions is essential for the continuation of the project and continued buy-in. Continued bedside team rounding, chart reviews, and data surveillance are necessary. Data surveillance will allow for monitoring of the measures, root cause analyses, and action plans for course correction. The infection preventionist shall disseminate quarterly CAUTI prevention data to key stakeholders using control charts. Ongoing hospital wide CAUTI education shall be provided during the annual nursing staff skills fair.

Timeline

Successful completion of this DNP project requires that the project team adhere to a defined timeline. The project spanned over a period of two months with three phases, from January 2021 to March 2021 (Table 1). The first phase of the project (pre-implementation or Phase one) was completed over one month (January 2021). Phase one was dedicated to the:

- Identification of the project's stakeholders
- Formation of the project team
- Identification of the CAUTI champions
- Education of the project team and champions
- Communication with ICU staff
- Completion of the pre-implementation nursing staff survey
- Completion of the pre-implementation SWOT analysis, and
- Pre-implementation and baseline data collection

The second phase of the project was conducted over 1 month (January 31, 2021 to March 1, 2021). Phase two of the project was the implementation of the pilot bundle of interventions.

During this phase, post-implementation data collection was performed. At the end of the latter phase, the project author focused on the:

- Evaluation of the project through pre- and post-implementation data analysis.
- Delineation of a maintenance plan through post-implementation data dissemination to the stakeholders. Table 1 shows the outline of the project's implementation timeline.

Table 1*Timeline*

Phases	Completion date	Planning	Pre-implementation	Implementation	Evaluation
Phase one	Jan. 2021 to Jan. 31, 2021	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Meeting with stakeholders (CNO, ICU Director, Charge nurses, Infection prevention, Nurse) -Formation of the project team -Identification of the CAUTI champions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Education of the project team and champions -Communication with ICU staff - Conduction of the pre-implementation nursing staff survey -Conduction of the pre-implementation SWOT analysis -Pre-implementation data collection 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ongoing communication with ICU staff, ICU leaders, CNO, Infection Prevention nurse, IT coordinator 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Data collection from nurses' surveys -Data collection from the SWOT analysis -Ongoing communication with ICU staff, ICU leaders, CNO, Infection Prevention nurse, IT coordinator
			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Baseline data collection <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Baseline compliance data collection -Baseline Foley catheter utilization rate, Foley catheter days, CAUTI events, CAUTI rates. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Ongoing communication with ICU staff, ICU leaders, CNO, Infection Prevention nurse 	
Phase two	Jan. 31 to March 1, 2021			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Ongoing tracking of data -Ongoing communication with ICU staff, ICU leaders, CNO, Infection Prevention nurse 	
				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Implementation of the Bundle of interventions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Bedside rounding and audits -Weekly chart reviews -Foley catheter removal reminders -patient/family education 	
	March 2021	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data analysis, evaluation, Dissemination of the results 			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data analysis - Dissemination of the results

Summary

This section summarized the steps and interventions that were undertaken to achieve the objectives of this DNP project. A description of the project ethical considerations, setting, sample, team, implementation procedures, measures, data collection, and evaluation were provided. The project author presented an overview of the project planning with a delineation of the pre- and post-implementation activities (project facility approval, IRB approval, and intervention timeline). After the DNP project committee, project facility and IRB approvals, the project author began its implementation. The author reported necessary adjustments that were made during the implementation.

Results

Nurses' Survey

Prior to implementing the bundle of interventions, an 11-question survey (Appendix D) was distributed to 47 RNs. There was a response rate of 95.7% (n=45). This survey identified the RN's perceptions regarding the barriers to the nurse driven CAUTI prevention protocol.

Demographics

The gender, age, level of education, licenses and certificates earned and years of experience in the project facility and in ICU were presented in Table 2. The majority of the RNs self-identified as female (71.1%, age 36 and older (75.5%), with 62% holding a bachelor's degree and 73.3% had no specialty certification (Table 4). Out of the 45 RNs who participated in the project, only seven were certified in critical care. Table 3 showed that ICU RNs had been working in the ICU and project facility between 11 and 12 years. Half of the participants had worked at the project facility for at least eight years (with 10 years or more in the ICU). The "typical" ICU RN at the project facility had worked within +/- 10.10 years with an average of 11.80 years. The least number of years of experience in both the project facility and the ICU was one year and the longest was 33 years (Table 3).

Table 2

Licenses

Licenses	Frequency	Percent
RN	45	100

Table 3*Years of experience at the project facility and in the ICU*

Locations	Mean	Median	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
At the project facility	11.80	8	10.10	1	33
In ICU	11.49	10	9.36	1	33

Table 4*Demographics*

Items	Frequency	Percent
Gender		
Female	32	71.1
Male	13	28.9
Total	45	100
Degree		
Associate Degree	10	22.2
Bachelor	28	62.2
Master	6	13.3
Doctorate	1	2.2
Total	45	100
Age		
18-25	0	0.0
26-35	11	24.4
36-50	19	42.2
Over 50	15	33.3
Total	45	100
Certifications		
CCRN	7	15.6
More than one, including CCRN	2	4.4
Other (Public Health Nurse)	3	6.7
None	33	73.3
Total	45	100

Nurses' Perceptions of Barriers to Implementing the CAUTI Prevention Protocol

To assess the nurses' perceptions toward the barriers to the CAUTI prevention protocol implementation, five-point Likert-style-questions were used to examine their views on the

protocol's ease of use, the education provided to them on the protocol, IUC shift hand-off practices, physicians' knowledge of proper indications for IUC use, and timely physicians' orders for IUC removal. Then, barriers to appropriate IUC use, aseptic IUC insertion, evidence based IUC maintenance, timely IUC removal, and proper IUC management documentation were evaluated.

Perception Toward CAUTI Prevention Protocol Education and Utilization

In a large majority, ICU's frontline RNs agreed that the hospital's current CAUTI prevention protocol was easy to use (71.1%); they felt that they were adequately educated on the use of the CAUTI prevention protocol (84.4%), and that IUCs were routinely addressed during shift handoffs (66.7%) (Table 5). Moreover, most of these nurses reported that ICU physicians know the proper indication for IUC use per-protocol (53.3%) and that IUC removal was timely ordered by physicians (51.1%) (Table 5). It is important to note that 22.2% and 28.9% of nurses reported respectively that physicians did not know the proper indications for Foley catheter use per the hospital protocol and that they did not timely order the removal of IUCs (Table 5).

Table 5*Perception Toward CAUTI Prevention Protocol Education and Utilization*

Items	Strongly Disagree		Disagree		Neither Agree nor Disagree		Agree		Strongly Agree	
	#	%	#	%	#	%	#	%	#	%
The hospital's current catheter associated urinary tract infection protocol is easy for nurses to utilize.	2	4.4	0	0.0	11	24.4	8	17.8	24	53.3
I was adequately educated on the hospital's current catheter associated urinary tract infection protocol.	2	4.4	1	2.2	4	8.9	11	24.4	27	60.0
Physicians do not know the proper indications for Foley catheter use per the protocol.	19	42.2	5	11.1	11	24.4	5	11.1	5	11.1
Physicians do not timely order removal of the Foley catheter.	14	31.1	9	20.0	9	20.0	9	20.0	4	8.9
During handoff indwelling catheters are routinely addressed.	4	8.9	5	11.1	6	13.3	12	26.7	18	40.0

Barriers to adherence to specific items of the CAUTI prevention protocol were examined. There were five questions with multiple associated checkboxes that respondents could choose to check or not check, indicating whether they believed the element associated with that checkbox presented a barrier to the CAUTI prevention protocol. Tables 6 to 10 present the frequency distributions for the multiple-choice checkboxes within each CAUTI prevention protocol item. In these frequency distributions tables, responses had been arranged from “most likely to be considered a barrier” to “least likely to be considered a barrier.”

Barriers to Appropriate IUC Use

Respondents were asked about their perceptions toward the various barriers that affected proper IUCs use. The top three reported barriers included concerns or prioritization related to patient safety issues (fall, incontinence dermatitis, etc.) (44.4%), lack or limited knowledge of

the protocol (33.3%), and IUC insertion practices and customs in the ICU (28.9%). Items that were the least likely to be considered barriers to appropriate IUC use were “Lack of proper physicians' education on the protocol” (11.1%) and “Patient and family requests for indwelling catheters” (6.7%) (Table 6).

Table 6

Barriers to Proper IUC Use

Items	Yes		No	
	#	%	#	%
Concerns or prioritization relative to other patient safety issues	20	44.4	25	55.6
Lack/limited knowledge of the protocol	15	33.3	30	66.7
Catheter insertion practices and customs in the ICU	13	28.9	32	71.1
Lack of proper frontline nurses' education on the protocol	12	26.7	33	73.3
Limited availability of Foley catheter alternatives	12	26.7	33	73.3
Lack of proper physicians' education on the protocol	5	11.1	40	88.9
Patient and family requests for indwelling catheters	3	6.7	42	93.3

Barriers to Aseptic Insertion of Foley Catheters

Table 7 showed the results for checklist items under barriers to aseptic Foley catheter insertion. The most commonly selected barrier was “Lack of manpower” (lack of assisting staff during the insertion process) at 42.2%. The other two most common barriers to aseptic insertion of IUC were “Lack of awareness of consequences of aseptic insertion violation,” (31.1%) and “lack of knowledge of the CAUTI prevention protocol (28.9%). The least commonly reported barriers were “Inconvenient or inconsistent location of hand cleaning gel/solution” and “Foley catheter insertion is a task rather than an evidence-based practice,” both with just 2.2%. Three RNs listed “other” barriers as well. Each of them respectively reported “patient inability to cooperate,” “patient with altered mental status,” and “lack of experience” (new grad).

Table 7*Barriers to Aseptic Insertion of Foley Catheters Insertion*

Items	Yes		No	
	#	%	#	%
Lack of manpower (lack of assisting staff during the insertion process)	19	42.2	26	57.8
Lack of awareness of consequences of aseptic insertion violation	14	31.1	31	68.9
Lack of knowledge of the protocol	13	28.9	32	71.1
Lack of skills	9	20.0	36	80.0
Lack of proper training on the protocol	8	17.8	37	82.2
Work environment constraints	4	8.9	41	91.1
Lack of space for sterile field set up	2	4.4	43	95.6
Lack of adequate supplies	2	4.4	43	95.6
Inconvenient or inconsistent location of hand cleaning gel/solution	1	2.2	44	97.8
Foley catheter insertion is a task rather than an evidence-based practice	1	2.2	44	97.8

Barriers to EB Foley Catheter Maintenance

Only 44 participants responded to the EB Foley catheter maintenance question (Question 8). Table 8 presents barriers to EB Foley catheter appropriate maintenance. The most commonly selected barrier was “Heavy nursing workload” with a strong majority of 72.7% of the respondents. This was followed by “Lack of time” (52.3% of participants) and lack of a standardized patient/family education tool for patient/family education (43.2%). The least commonly reported barriers were “Unclear/difficult protocol/guidelines” (9.1%), “Lack of supplies” (9.1%), and “Catheterized patients/family not educated on FC maintenance and infection prevention barriers” (selected by 6.8% of respondents).

Table 8*Barriers to EB Foley Catheter Maintenance*

Items	Yes		No	
	#	%	#	%
Heavy nursing workload	32	72.7	12	27.3
Lack of time	23	52.3	21	47.7

Lack of a standardized patient/family education tool for patient/family education	19	43.2	25	56.8
Inadequate staffing	11	25.0	33	75.0
Limited EB knowledge/skills of Foley catheter maintenance	8	18.2	36	81.8
Lack of training on EB Foley catheter maintenance	5	11.4	39	88.6
Uncleared/difficult protocol/guidelines	4	9.1	40	90.9
Lack of supplies	4	9.1	40	90.9
Catheterized patients/family not educated on FC maintenance and infection prevention barriers	3	6.8	41	93.2

Barriers to Timely Removal of Foley Catheters

Only 44 participants responded to questions related to barriers to timely removal of IUCs. The most commonly reported barriers included “heavy nurse workload” (by a large majority of 63.6% of respondents), lack of timely physician order for removal (59.1%), lack of physician routine review of Foley catheter necessity (40.9%), catheter removal not considered a priority (38.6%), and lack of agreement on standard protocols and indications for removal (29.5%) (see Table 9).

Table 9

Barriers to Timely Removal of Foley Catheters

Items	Yes		No	
	#	%	#	%
Heavy nursing workload	28	63.6	16	36.4
Lack of timely physician orders for removal	26	59.1	18	40.9
Physicians not routinely reviewing catheter necessity during rounds	18	40.9	26	59.1
Catheter removal not considered a priority	17	38.6	27	61.4
There is a lack of agreement on and awareness of standard protocols, and indications for removal	13	29.5	31	70.5
Confusion exists about who has authority to remove catheters	7	15.9	37	84.1
Communication barriers among clinicians create challenges	6	13.6	38	86.4
Catheters going unnoticed or hidden under clothing	2	4.5	42	95.5
Little or no discussion of catheters among clinicians	2	4.5	42	95.5
Catheter data are hard to find, not accurate, or not available	1	2.3	43	97.7

Barriers to Proper Documentation

Only 44 participants responded to Question 10 (Barriers to Proper Documentation). Examining the barriers to proper documentation as prescribed by the CAUTI prevention protocol, yielded the following factors: workload concerns (spending more time charting) (70% of participants), lack of time (56.8%), and documentation prompts not available on the worklist (36.4%) (Table 10).

Table 10

Barriers to Proper Documentation

Items	Yes		No	
	#	%	#	%
Workload (concerns of spending more time charting)	31	70.5	13	29.5
Lack of time	25	56.8	19	43.2
Documentation prompts not available on the worklist	16	36.4	28	63.6
Lack of adequate staffing	14	31.8	30	68.2
Lack of computer skills	4	9.1	40	90.9
Work environment constraints	4	9.1	40	90.9

Figure 2 summarizes common reported barriers to individual items of the CAUTI prevention protocol.

Figure 2

Common Barriers to Individual Items of the CAUTI Prevention Protocol

Identified Barriers to Protocol (Nurses' Survey)	Appropriate Use	Aseptic Insertion	Appropriate Maintenance	Timely Removal	Proper Documentation
Concerns or prioritization related to patient safety issues (Falls, incontinence dermatitis)	●				
Lack/limited knowledge of the protocol	●	●			
Catheter insertion practices and customs in the ICU	●				
Lack of assisting staff during insertion		●			
Lack of awareness of aseptic insertion violation consequences		●			
Heavy nursing workload			●	●	●

Table 11 summarized the four most common barriers to the implementation of the CAUTI prevention protocol identified by a vast majority of ICU nurses.

Table 11

Most Common Barriers to Nurse Adherence to the CAUTI Prevention Protocol

Barriers to CAUTI prevention protocol	Percentage of Respondents
Heavy nursing workload	72.7
Workload concerns (spending more time charting)	70
Lack of timely physician order for removal	59.1
Lack of time	56.8

The most common reported barriers to the CAUTI prevention protocol implementation included heavy nursing load (72,7% of respondents), spending more time charting (70%), lack of timely physician order for Foley catheter removal (59.1%), and lack of time (56.8%).

Daily Rounding and Chart Reviews

The daily rounding checklist had 10 items (although the last item did not apply to all patients) and the electronic chart review checklist had 7 items. Checklist items were first analyzed individually, then combined.

Daily Rounding

Adherence rates of each of the 10 individual daily rounding checklist items were examined. Table 12 showed the frequency distribution adherence rates to each of the 10 items both pre- and post-implementation.

Table 12*Adherence to Individual 10-Item Daily Rounding Checklist, Pre- and Post-Implementation*

Items	Time	Not Completed		Completed		Total
		#	%	#	%	
1. The indwelling urinary catheter used for an appropriate indication	Pre	21	4.0%	499	96.0%	520
	Post	1	0.2%	406	99.8%	407
2. Necessity for continuing the indwelling urinary catheter assessed	Pre	109	21.0%	411	79.0%	520
	Post	3	0.7%	404	99.3%	407
3. Seal between the catheter and collecting tubing intact	Pre	6	1.2%	514	98.8%	520
	Post	0	0.0%	407	100.0%	407
4. Catheter tubing unobstructed and not twisted, kinked, or looped	Pre	1	0.2%	519	99.8%	520
	Post	0	0.0%	407	100.0%	407
5. Urine collection bag below the level of the bladder	Pre	1	0.2%	519	99.8%	520
	Post	1	0.2%	406	99.8%	407
6. Catheter secured to the patient	Pre	2	0.4%	518	99.6%	520
	Post	0	0.0%	407	100.0%	407
7. Catheter not touching the floor	Pre	34	6.5%	486	93.5%	520
	Post	1	0.2%	406	99.8%	407
8. Catheter bag no more than 2/3 full	Pre	78	15.0%	442	85.0%	520
	Post	1	0.2%	406	99.8%	407
9. Daily perineal care completed	Pre	2	0.4%	518	99.6%	520
	Post	0	0.0%	407	100.0%	407
10. Patient &/or family provided with education handout within 24 hours of insertion	Pre	0	0.0%	1	100.0%	1
	Post	0	0.0%	125	100.0%	125

During the post-implementation period, RNs were compliant to implementing the majority of daily rounding checklist items, the majority of the time (most of the adherence rates > 99.5 %, five items with the perfect adherence rates of 100%). Item 2 (“Necessity for continuing the indwelling urinary catheter assessed”) was not followed on three occasions, leading to an adherence rate of 99.3%, ($p < 0.001$), which was the lowest of all the post-implementation adherence rates. In the pre-implementation period however, several of daily rounding checklist items were completed less than 95% of the time. These items were item two (79%, the lowest adherence rate, $p < 0.001$), item 8 (“Catheter bag no more than 2/3 full”), which

was performed 85% of the time, and item 7 (“Catheter not touching the floor”) (93.4%, $p < 0.001$). All post-implementation individual adherence rates improved except item 5 (Urine collection bag below the level of the bladder) which had an adherence rate that did not change (98.8% pre- and post-implementation. It was important to note that pre- and post-implementation adherence to item 10 was not compared since nurses did not provide the standardized educational handout to patient/family on day one post Foley catheter insertion. None of the patients was alert in the pre-implementation phase. Furthermore, family visits were not authorized during the entire length of the project due to COVID-19 pandemic surge. Results from the Chi-squared test and Fisher exact test for each of the 10 items were provided in Table 13. In some cases, a Fisher’s exact test was used instead of a Chi-squared test because some of the numbers in the table were small.

Table 13

Individual Daily Rounding Checklist Items Chi-Squared and Fisher’s Exact Tests Results

Items	χ^2	df	P	Fisher Exact p
Item 1	14.175	1	< 0.001	
Item 2	87.913	1	< 0.001	
Item 3				0.038
Item 4				1.000
Item 5				1.000
Item 6				0.507
Item 7	24.884	1	< 0.001	
Item 8	63.752	1	< 0.001	
Item 9				0.507
Item 10	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A

Table 13 showed that during the post-intervention period, there were statistically significant positive changes in how often nurses were compliant to items 1, 2, 7, and 8 ($p < 0.001$), and item 3 ($p < 0.038$). The adherence rates for these items were greater following post-implementation. It was important to note that item 10 could not be tested because this item did not apply to any case

prior to the implementation. A run chart was used to display these findings. Figure 2 showed the daily rounding checklist items adherence rates.

Figure 3

Adherence to the Overall Daily Rounding Checklist Items

As seen in Figure 2, during the pre-implementation phase there was a lot of variability in the adherence rates (percentage of protocol items that were completed). The protocol items outlined in the rounding checklist were rarely followed, with the majority of adherence rates < 80% ($p < 0.001$). Following the implementation of the bundle of interventions, the percentage of completed items across daily rounding checklists was higher (often 100%), with less variation than in the pre-implementation phase. Pre-implementation lowest adherence rate was 0%, meaning that the nurse did not follow any of rounding checklist items as required by the hospital protocol. Post-implementation lowest was about 85%. All pre-implementation and all post-implementation rounding checklist items were combined and evaluated as seen in Table 14. A

nurse was compliant if all seven checklist items were completed/checked “Yes.” Table 14 displayed the results.

Table 14

Adherence to the Overall Daily Rounding Checklist Items

Time		Not All Completed	All Completed	Total
Pre-implementation	Count	190	330	520
	%	36.5%	63.5%	
Post-implementation	Count	5	402	407
	%	1.2%	98.8%	

In order to determine whether adherence rates for daily rounding checklist items had changed in a statistically significant way between pre- and post-implementation, a Chi-squared test statistical analysis performed. The p -value was < 0.001 . The results of the chi-square test are presented in Table 15.

Table 15

Daily Rounding Chi-Squared Test Results

χ^2	Df	P
171.367	1	< 0.001

The Chi-squared test results in Table 15 showed a statistically significant positive change in the daily rounding checklist items adherence rate ($\chi^2(1) = 171.37, p < 0.001$). This rate increased following the implementation of the bundle of interventions. Out of the 520-pre-implementation daily rounding audit cases, the daily rounding checklist items were followed properly 330 times (adherence rate of 63.5%, $P < 0.001$). Out of the post-intervention’s 407 audit cases, daily rounding checklist items were fully completed 402 times, with a correlated post-intervention phase’s adherence rate of 98.8% ($p < 0.001$). There was a significant increase of

35.3% ($p < 0.001\%$), (from 63.5 to 98.8%, $p < 0.001$) in the post-intervention adherence rate when compared to the pre-implementation rate.

Electronic Chart Reviews

Electronic chart reviews were completed. There were seven electronic chart review checklist items. Adherence rates of each of the seven individual chart checklist items were examined. Table 16 showed the frequency distribution adherence rates for each of the seven items both pre- and post-implementation.

Table 16

Adherence to Individual 7-Item Chart Review Checklist, Pre- and Post-Implementation

Item	Time	Not Completed		Completed		Total
		#	%	#	%	
1. Indwelling urinary catheter insertion/start documented (Started in MediTech)	Pre	32	6.2%	488	93.8%	520
	Post	0	0.0%	407	100.0%	407
2. Indwelling urinary catheter used for an appropriate indication	Pre	58	11.2%	462	88.8%	520
	Post	6	1.5%	401	98.5%	407
3. Necessity for continuing the indwelling urinary catheter documented	Pre	129	24.8%	391	75.2%	520
	Post	2	0.5%	405	99.5%	407
4. Daily perineal care documented	Pre	38	7.3%	482	92.7%	520
	Post	1	0.2%	406	99.8%	407
5. Urine assessment documented (output and character)	Pre	40	7.7%	480	92.3%	520
	Post	0	0.0%	407	100.0%	407
6. Urinary catheter assessment documented (type & size)	Pre	40	7.7%	480	92.3%	520
	Post	0	0.0%	407	100.0%	407
7. Patient &/or family education documented	Pre	147	28.3%	373	71.7%	520
	Post	6	1.5%	401	98.5%	407

A Chi-squared test was performed for each of the seven individual chart review checklist items. Results were provided in Table 17.

Table 17*Individual Chart Review Checklist Items Chi-Squared Test Results*

Items	χ	df	P
Item 1	25.942	1	< 0.001
Item 2	33.282	1	< 0.001
Item 3	111.247	1	< 0.001
Item 4	28.252	1	< 0.001
Item 5	32.720	1	< 0.001
Item 6	32.684	1	< 0.001
Item 7	118.819	1	< 0.001

All items had significant p -values (0.001), indicating that there were statistically significant positive changes in how often nurses were compliant to each item of the chart review checklist. Post-implementation, there was an improvement in adherence rates of all individual chart review checklist. All the nurses fully complied to items 1, 5, and 6 (adherence rate of 100%, $p < 0.001$, for each of these items). The lowest adherence rate was 98.5%, $p < 0.001$ (items 2 and 7). Pre-implementation, individual item adherence rates were between 71.7% (item 7) to 93.8% ($p < 0.001$) (item 1). All adherence rates for each chart review checklist items were greater following implementation, with a $P < 0.001$ for each of these items.

An overall chart review adherence rate of checklist items was evaluated. The IUC chart review checklist items were followed if all 7 items were checked “Yes” (completed). Adherence rates were calculated. Results are displayed in a run chart (Figure 4).

Figure 4

Adherence to the Overall Chart Review Checklist Items

Prior to the project implementation, there was a lot of variability in the chart review checklist items adherence rates and nurses were never compliant to these items 100% of the time. While most of the adherence rates were under 60% ($p < 0.001$), the lowest was 30% ($p < 0.001$). Following the project implementation, while there were still some variabilities, the adherence rates across all the chart review audits improved (with most of them up to 100%) ($p < 0.001$) and there was less variability than in the pre-project implementation phase (Figure 2). The lower post-implementation adherence rate was 50% ($p < 0.001$).

To determine whether overall adherence rates for chart review checklist items had changed in a statistically significant way between pre- and post-implementation, all pre-implementation and post-implementation chart review checklist items were combined and evaluated as seen in Table 18. These overall chart review checklist items adherence rates

increased from 54.4% to 96.8 % ($p < 0.001$) following the implementation of the bundle of activities, with a substantial post-implementation rate increase of 42.4 % ($p < 0.001$) (Table 18).

Table 18

Adherence to the Chart Review Checklist Items, Pre- and Post-Implementation

Time		Correct Electronic Chart Protocol		
		Not Completed	Completed	Total
Pre-implementation	Count	237	283	520
	%	45.6%	54.4%	
Post-implementation	Count	13	394	407
	%	3.2%	96.8%	

However, to determine if the change was due to a random chance a Chi-squared test was conducted. Results are presented in Table 19. Table 19 showed that the p value is 0.001, demonstrating that there was a statistically significant positive change in the overall chart review checklist items adherence rates, with a 42.4 % increase ($p < 0.001$).

Table 19

Chart Review Checklist Items Chi-Squared Test Results

χ^2	Df	p
208.223	1	<0.001

Overall Adherence to the CAUTI Prevention Protocol

The daily rounding and electronic chart review checklist items adherence were combined in an analysis to examine nurses' adherence to the full CAUTI prevention protocol items. Each case (combination) had 17 items from individual daily rounding and chart review checklist items combined. For each individual full audit, a nurse was identified as compliant to the CAUTI prevention protocol if all 17 related items (daily rounding and chart review checklist items

combined) were checked “yes” (completed). The percentages of completed CAUTI prevention protocol items were evaluated pre- and post-implementation. The run chart in Figure 5 showed the adherence rates for the CAUTI prevention protocol pre- and post-implementation.

Figure 5

Adherence to the Full CAUTI Prevention Protocol

Pre-implementation, there was variability in the daily implementation of the CAUTI prevention protocol items. The protocol was never followed correctly. Adherence rates ranged from 0% (non-compliance to all the CAUTI prevention protocol items) to approximately 79%, with many of these rates being under 60% ($p < 0.001$). Post-implementation, while there was still some variability (less than in the pre-implementation phase), the adherence rates across all audited items improved substantially with most of them up to 100% ($p < 0.001$). The lowest post-implementation CAUTI prevention adherence rate was 50% ($p < 0.001$). To determine if the percentages of compliance cases had changed in a statistically significant manner between pre-

and post-implementation, all pre-implementation and post-implementation audits cases were combined and evaluated as in Table 20.

Table 20

Adherence to the Full CAUTI Prevention Protocol

Time		No	Yes	Total
Pre-implementation	Count	308	212	520
	% within Pre	59.2%	40.8%	
Post-implementation	Count	16	391	407
	% within Post	3.9%	96.1%	

Of the 520-pre-implementation combined daily rounding/chart review audits (one audit was a combination of 17 items), the CAUTI prevention protocol was fully followed 212 times (40.8% of the time only), with a consecutive adherence rate of 40.8%. Post-implementation, of the 407 audits (one audit was 17 items combined), nurses were fully compliant to the CAUTI prevention protocol 391 times. Overall nurses' adherence rate was 96.1%, with a 55.3% improvement. However, to determine whether this change was statistically significant, a Chi-squared test was performed. The result of the Chi-squared test was presented in Table 21.

Table 21

Results of Chi-Squared Test for the Full Adherence to the CAUTI Prevention Protocol

χ^2	df	p
307.085	1	< 0.001

The p value was < 0.001 meaning that all pre- and post- implementation results were statistically significant. Post-implementation, there was a statistically significant increase of the

overall nurses' adherence to the CAUTI prevention protocol (55.3%, $p < 0.001$) from 40.8 to 96.1%.

Catheter Days and Catheter Utilization Rates

Pre- and post-implementation Foley Catheter days and patient days data were provided by Infection Prevention Services. These data were shown in Table 22, along with the weekly calculated catheter utilization rates (catheter days divided by patient days, times 1,000, to create catheter utilization rates per 1,000 patient days).

Table 22

Weekly Foley Catheter Data, Pre- and Post-Implementation

Time	Week	Catheter Days	Patient Days	Catheter Utilization Rate (per 1,000 patient days)
Pre-implementation	1	169	181	933.70
	2	135	168	803.57
	3	109	151	721.85
	4	106	136	779.41
Post-implementation	1	137	148	925.68
	2	134	163	822.09
	3	72	105	685.71
	4	63	81	777.78

Figure 6 was a run chart presenting pre- and post-implementation weekly Foley catheter days (without adjustment).

Figure 6*Weekly Foley Catheter Days (Not Adjusted)*

Figure 7 is a run chart showing weekly Foley catheter utilization rates (catheter days adjusted by patient days).

Figure 7*Weekly Foley Catheter Utilization Rates*

In Figure 6, when examining catheter days alone, it appeared that IUCs were used less during the post-implementation period, when compared to the pre-implementation period. When examining Table 22, it was clear that there were fewer patient days during the post-implementation period as well. After adjusting for patient days (catheter utilization rates in Figure 7), there was no substantial difference between pre and post implementation (816.04 vs 816.90/1000 catheter days). Table 23 combined all four weeks pre- and post-implementation catheter days, patient days and catheter utilization rates, so the totals could be compared directly.

Table 23*Overall Catheter Data, Pre- and Post-Implementation*

Implementation Time	Catheter Days	Patient Days	Catheter Utilization Rates (per 1,000 patient days)
Pre	519	636	816.04
Post	406	497	816.90

Unadjusted, catheter days seemed to have decreased post-implementation from 519 to 406. However, because patient days had also decreased pre-implementation, both variables were adjusted to assess the actual statistical change. After the adjustment, both pre- and post-implementation catheter utilization rates were similar, respectively 816.04 vs 816.90/1000 catheter days ($p = 1.000$). This result was presented using the bar chart in Figure 8 below.

Figure 8*Overall Catheter Utilization Rates, Pre- and Post-Implementation*

To determine whether there was a statistically significant difference between both pre- and post-implementation catheter utilization rates, a Poisson exact test was performed using R version 4.0.3. The Poisson exact test result was a p -value of 1.000, indicating that if the

underlying catheter utilization rates were the same, there was a 100% chance there would be a difference between the pre- and post-implementation periods at least as large as the one that was seen in these specific data. This conclusion was true since both pre- and post-implementation catheter utilization rates were remarkably similar, with no substantial change. This result confirmed that there was no statistically significant change between the pre- and post-implementation catheter utilization rates ($p = 1.000$).

Discussion and Recommendations

Discussion

The nurses' survey aimed to assess their perceptions of the barriers to the implementation of the CAUTI prevention protocol. For this evaluation, the survey responses were grouped into six categories including perceptions toward the protocol ease and use, barriers to appropriate Foley catheter use, barriers to aseptic Foley catheter insertion, barriers to EB Foley catheter maintenance, barriers to timely Foley catheter removal, and barriers to proper documentation. Most RNs indicated that the facility's CAUTI prevention protocol was easy to use (71.1%), they were adequately educated on the use of the CAUTI prevention protocol (84.4%), and that IUCs were routinely addressed during shift handoffs (66.7%). However, the results showed that 33.3% of the nurses indicated that they lacked knowledge and 26.7% indicated they lacked proper education on the CAUTI prevention protocol. Moreover, most of these nurses reported that ICU physicians knew the proper indications for IUC (53.3%).

Reported barriers to appropriate IUC use included concerns or prioritization related to patient safety issues (falls, incontinence dermatitis), lack or limited knowledge of the protocol, catheter insertion practices and customs in the ICU (ICU nurses tend to use Foley catheter in a systematic manner). For the barriers to the aseptic insertion of IUCs, nurses commonly reported that they lacked assisting staff during the Foley catheter insertion, some nurses were not aware of the consequences of aseptic insertion violation, and they had limited knowledge of the CAUTI prevention protocol. Factors that nurses considered to be major barriers to EB Foley catheter maintenance were workload and lack of time. Timely removal of IUCs was considered to be negatively impacted by heavy nurses' workload, lack of timely physician order for removal, lack of physician routine review of Foley catheter necessity, and IUC removal not considered a

priority by ICU nurses. Furthermore, workload concerns (spending more time charting), lack of time, and lack of documentation prompts on nurses' worklist were identified as barriers to proper IUC care documentation.

There were 22.2% of the nurses who reported that physicians did not know the proper indications for IUC use per the hospital protocol. These percentages are small, but it is important to note that physicians hold a crucial role in CAUTI prevention initiatives and should be aware of EB IUC indications and the importance of timely removal of Foley catheter in preventing CAUTI events. Additionally, for the question related to barriers to timely removal of IUCs (Table 9) most respondents (59.1%) asserted that physicians did not timely order IUC removals, while in one of the 5-point Likert questions, the majority of participants (51.1 %) (Table 5) indicated that physicians did timely order IUC removals. Per the CAUTI prevention protocol, a nurse should remove an IUC as soon as it did not meet the indication criteria. It appeared that the implementation of a nurse driven CAUTI prevention protocol may have increased or created confusion about who has formal responsibility for timely IUCs removal.

Post-implementation, there was a statistically significant improvement in nurses' adherence to the daily rounding checklist items (35.4%, $p < 0.001$), and to the chart review checklist items (42.4 %, $p < 0.001$). Overall, nurses' adherence to the full CAUTI prevention protocol items showed a substantial increase of 55.3% ($p < 0.001$). Unadjusted, catheter days seemed to have decreased post-implementation. However, when adjusted with patient days, there was no statistically significant change between the pre- and post-implementation catheter utilization rates ($p = 1.000$). While the overall nurses' adherence to the CAUTI prevention protocol had substantially increased post-implementation (55.3%), Foley catheter utilization

rates did not significantly change/decrease post-implementation (816.04 vs 816.90/1000 patient days, $p = 1.000$).

It is important to note that the project implementation coincided with the Winter and Spring 2020 COVID-19 pandemic surge. The COVID-19 surge was an extraneous factor that led to increased hospitalizations and patient acuity levels, which in-turn led to increased Foley catheter use and days, as noted during the first 2 weeks post-project implementation (Table 22). The increase in Foley catheter days mirrored the two-week peak of the COVID-19 surge in Los Angeles County. With the acuity level and length of stay of the patients hospitalized in the ICU increasing, patients needed a Foley catheter more often than usual. This might explain why there was no actual change in catheter utilization rates even though nurses were more compliant to the CAUTI prevention protocol post-implementation. There was one CAUTI event that occurred during the pre-implementation phase of the project, while none occurred in the post-implementation period. Since there was a daily assessment of catheter care and documentation during the post-implementation phase, nurses became more compliant to the CAUTI prevention protocol items. This increased compliance led to improved IUC care, ultimately preventing CAUTI event occurrences.

Recommendations

Specific interventions that could remove barriers to the CAUTI prevention protocol use and close the gap in the protocol adherence rates may include initiatives designed to improve catheter care awareness, such as EMR alerts to signal IUCs that have been in for several days. Furthermore, checklists, electronic reminders and stop orders, and tools to facilitate handoff and discussions might increase adherence rates. Recommendations from project observations, implementation and findings included:

- The creation of an EMR 48-hour stop order and removal prompts to allow for frequent reassessment of the necessity for an IUC and for timely IUC removals,
- The provision of an IUC care documentation prompt in RNs' worklist in the EMR,
- The implementation of an interdisciplinary daily rounding addressing the necessity of Foley catheters in place,
- The continuous IUC care assessment and documentation through daily rounding and chart reviews using audit checklists to promote interdisciplinary communication,
- The creation and implementation of a standard EB Foley catheter removal protocol and algorithm, along with badge buddies to empower frontline RNs' and delineate their responsibility in timely removal of an unnecessary IUC,
- The incorporation of CAUTI prevention measures in the annual nursing skills fair with annual evaluation of frontline RNs' competency on CAUTI prevention practices,
- The re-education of all nurses and physicians on CAUTI prevention protocol content, with a complementary annual refresher through the facility's e-learning modules system,
- The systematic provision of CAUTI prevention education to patient/family after ICU insertion using the standardized patient/family handout (Appendix L) provided during this project implementation.

Limitations, Strengths, and Conclusion

Limitations

There were several limitations identified in this DNP project. First, it was implemented in only one unit at one facility. Therefore, it may not be applicable in all settings. However, we believe this unit is similar in many ways to other hospital units since the use of IUCs are widespread. The project's duration was shortened due to the COVID-19 pandemic winter and spring 2021 surge. The initial planned duration of the project was six months (three months for period); however, this was shortened to two months for pre- and post- implementation due to the facility's tightened student clinical requirements in response to the COVID-19 surge. A longer project duration would have allowed for a larger patient sample, observations, and data collection. Another exogenous factor that likely affected the findings was the increased patient acuity associated with the Winter and Spring 2021 COVID-19 surge.

There were associated increases in ICU patient acuity and length of stay, nurses' workload (the patient/nurse ratio was often 3:1 instead of 2:1), Foley catheter use, and Foley catheter days, despite the statistically significant substantial increase in nurses' adherence to the CAUTI prevention protocol. Moreover, the systematic use of the standardized patient/family education handout was challenging, since most ICU patients were not alert, family visits were not allowed and family - ICU team communications were via phone, brief, and limited to discussing health status changes and plan of care. The standardized patient/family education handout implementation was therefore not assessed pre- and post-project implementation.

Strengths

The project design, which included piloting the intervention within the ICU and conducting data collection from multiple sources (nurses' surveys, daily rounding observations, electronic

chart reviews, and data mining from the EMR) strengthened the project's findings. Furthermore, the use of both observational and interview methods along with the triangulation of data collected from the different sources enriched the results, reduced the potential of bias, and strengthened the validity of the project's findings. The inclusion of ICU leadership (charge nurses and ICU director), CAUTI prevention champions, and the infection preventionist in the project team helped to ensure continued buy-in, increasing the sustainability of the project.

Conclusion

Catheter-associated urinary tract infections increase hospitals' costs and have been shown to increase morbidity and mortality while negatively impacting patients' satisfaction. Developing a standardized and systematic EB approaches for IUC utilization, maintenance, and removal using a CAUTI prevention protocol, along with a bundle of care interventions, had shown to decrease CAUTI incidences. Providing a clear pathway for nurse driven IUC removal along with an ongoing CAUTI prevention protocol adherence monitoring is essential to ensure that safe practices are fully embedded in the care of IUC patients.

This DNP project not only provided a deeper understanding of frontline nurses' challenges to implementing a nurse driven CAUTI prevention protocol, but it evaluated nurses' adherence to the protocol, assessed nurse's compliance after the implementation of bundle activities aiming to promote adherence to the protocol, and evaluated consecutive Foley catheter days and Foley catheter utilization rates. Future interventions are needed to clearly delineate clinicians' roles and responsibilities for proper use and removal of IUCs, to standardize IUC removal algorithms, and to develop effective tools to improve IUC risks awareness. Continuous evaluation and monitoring of nurses' barriers to CAUTI prevention protocols are crucial to decrease IUC use and improve IUC care in hospital settings.

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APPENDIX A

Project Facility's CAUTI Prevention Protocol

**DIGNITY HEALTH
ADMINISTRATIVE POLICY MANUAL
CLINICAL POLICY AND PROCEDURE**

TITLE: Urinary Catheter and Bladder Management

POLICY NUMBER: 100.8.002 **EFFECTIVE DATE:** March 20, 2019

APPLIES TO: System Offices **ORIGINAL EFFECTIVE DATE:** August 9, 2017
 Acute Care Entities
 Non-Acute Care Entities

POLICY:

It is the policy of Dignity Health to ensure the health and safety of patients through the use of evidence based practice and national guidelines to manage indwelling urinary catheters (IUC) and reduce unnecessary urinary catheterization. Indwelling urinary catheters shall be inserted only when indicated and removed as soon as possible to prevent catheter associated urinary tract infections (CAUTIs).

DEFINITIONS:

Licensed Independent Practitioner (LIP): means an individual, as permitted by law and regulation, and also by the organization, to provide care and services without direction or supervision within the scope of the individual's license and consistent with the privileges granted by the organization.

AFFECTED DEPARTMENTS:

All acute care nursing units caring for patients with indwelling urinary catheters.

PROCEDURE:

1. A LIP order is required for the insertion of an indwelling urinary catheter.
2. The indwelling urinary catheter, when appropriate, shall be inserted (See Facility policy and procedure for Urinary catheter insertion, care and maintenance)
 - a. A sterile, closed drainage collection system shall be used and maintained per policy.
 - b. An approved securement device shall be utilized.
 - c. Educate the patient or patient representative as appropriate on the indications for a urinary catheter, the procedure and the necessity for timely removal of the indwelling urinary catheter.

3. Nursing Assessment and Interventions
- a. RN shall assess the patient every shift and upon transfer to a lower acuity unit (e.g., ICU to Telemetry) to determine if the patient continues to meet criteria for a urinary catheter. Examples may include, but are not limited to:
 - Urinary retention
 - Urinary obstruction
 - Critical Care Patients Only: Strict output monitoring that cannot be achieved by Foley alternative
 - Genitourinary tract surgery / Pelvic Surgery
 - Surgical patients (remove by post-op day 2)
 - Acute phase genitalia wounds
 - To aid in healing of Stage 3 and 4 pressure ulcers that cannot be kept dry utilizing standard protocol
 - End of life comfort care orders in place for terminally ill patient
 - Epidural catheter in place
 - b. If the patient fits any one of the criterion above, document the appropriate justification in the patient's medical record and do NOT remove urinary catheter.
4. Discontinuation/Removal of Indwelling Urinary Catheter
- a. Patients who are identified as being anuric for >2 days should have their urinary catheter discontinued.
 - b. If the patient does not meet criteria for retaining/maintaining an indwelling urinary catheter and there is not a specific LIP order to continue the catheter, the Registered Nurse (RN) shall remove the indwelling urinary catheter.
 - Consider other means of bladder management including an appropriate toileting plan, external male catheters, female urinals, and peri-pads for incontinent women
 - If the RN is uncertain as to whether to remove the indwelling urinary catheter, the LIP shall be contacted
 - c. If the patient meets criteria for removal of the IUC, the RN shall:
 - Provide patient education prior to removal
 - Utilize appropriate technique for catheter removal and
 - Document in the patient's medical record the time the indwelling urinary catheter was removed.
 - d. Void residual volumes shall be monitored at least every six (6) hours post IUC removal.
 - If the patient voids a total of ≥ 300 ml within 6 hours, no action is required.
 - If the patient voids < 300 ml within 6 hours and shows any one of the following signs or symptoms of urinary retention:
 - bladder distention
 - lower abdominal discomfort
 - urge to void but cannot
 - frequent urination with small amounts

Proceed to straight catheterization and record volume. (Utilize a bladder scanner, if available, to assess and record residual volume prior to performing straight catheterization.)

- Notify LIP if the patient continues to exhibit lower abdominal discomfort, has the urge to void but cannot, has frequent urination with small amounts, or becomes incontinent. If the patient voids < 300ml within 6 hours and the patient does not have signs/symptoms of retention and the patient is not uncomfortable, then encourage voiding, fluid intake, repositioning.
 - Reassess within three (3) hours. If the patient still has not voided, then proceed to straight catheterization and record volume. (Utilize a bladder scanner, if available, to assess and record residual volume within 6 hours and prior to performing straight catheterization if available.)
- e. Bedside evaluation of the suprapubic area shall be completed at minimum every shift for any fullness or lower abdominal discomfort or when the patient has the urge to void but cannot.

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STATUTORY/REGULATORY AUTHORITIES: *None cited*

**DIGNITY HEALTH
PROTOCOL**

TITLE: Urinary Catheter and Bladder Management Protocol

ASSOCIATED DOCUMENTS: Urinary Catheter and Bladder Management Policy # 100.8.002

CRITERIA FOR IMPLEMENTATION: A clinician order for "Foley Cath Protocol"

PROTOCOL:

STEP 1 Assess patient every shift and upon transfer to lower acuity unit to determine if the patient continues to meet the need for a urinary catheter

Criteria for insertion or continuation of an indwelling urinary catheter:

NOTE: If the patient fits any one of the criterion below, document the appropriate justification in the patient's medical record and do NOT remove the urinary catheter.

- Urinary Retention
- Urinary obstruction
- Critical Care Patients Only: Strict output monitoring that cannot be achieved by Foley alternative
- Genitourinary (GU) tract surgery/Pelvic Surgery
- Surgical patients (remove by post-op day 2)
- Acute phase genitalia wounds
- To aid in healing of Stage III or Stage IV pressure ulcers that cannot be kept dry utilizing standard protocol
- End of life comfort care orders in place for terminally ill patient
- Epidural catheter in place

STEP 2 If NONE of the above criteria are met and there is no specific clinician order to continue the catheter, the RN is to discontinue the urinary catheter following this protocol

- Patients who are identified as being anuric for >2 days should have their urinary catheter discontinued.
- Document in the patient's medical record the time the indwelling urinary catheter was removed.

*If the RN is uncertain as to whether to remove the indwelling urinary catheter, the Provider shall be contacted.

STEP 3 Assess and monitor void residuals and bladder distention post urinary catheter removal*

Void residual volumes shall be monitored at least every 6 hours post urinary catheter removal:

- If the patient voids a total of ≥ 300 ml within 6 hours, no action is required.
- If patient voids < 300 ml within 6 hours and the patient shows signs and symptoms of one of the following:
 - bladder distention
 - lower abdominal discomfort
 - urge to void but cannot
 - frequent urination with small amounts

The RN shall proceed to straight catheterization and record volume. (Utilize a bladder scanner, if available, to assess and record residual volume prior to performing straight catheterization). Notify the Provider if the patient continues to exhibit lower abdominal discomfort, has the urge to void but cannot, has frequent urination with small amounts, or becomes incontinent.

- If the patient voids < 300 ml within 6 hours and the patient does NOT have signs/symptoms of retention and the patient is not uncomfortable then encourage voiding, fluid intake, repositioning, and reassess 3 hours later.
 - If the patient still has not voided, then proceed to straight catheterization and record volume. (Utilize a bladder scanner, if available, to assess and record residual volume within 6 hours and prior to performing straight catheterization if available).
- Bedside evaluation of the supra pubic area shall be completed at minimum every shift for any fullness or lower abdominal discomfort or when the patient has the urge to void but cannot.

*Contact the Provider if the patient's condition changes or if uncertain how to manage post catheter removal residuals/symptoms.

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Effective Date: May 16, 2019

Reviewed With No Changes: July 6, 2020

PROTOCOL: Urinary Catheter and Bladder Management

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APPENDIX B

Iowa Model

The Iowa Model Revised: Evidence-Based Practice to Promote Excellence in Health Care

Iowa model of evidence-based practice: revisions and validation (Iowa Model Collaborative, 2017).

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Letter of Permission to Use the Iowa Model

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Kimberly Jordan - University of Iowa Hospitals and Clinics <noreply@qemailserver.com>
to me ▾

Apr 16, 2020, 11:56 AM

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APPENDIX C

IRB Approval

Office Memorandum

DATE: December 11, 2020

TO: Glenn Raup, RN, PhD, MBA, MSN, CEN

FROM: Claire Bakewell

PROJECT TITLE: [1669326-1] Nurses' Adherence to a Nurse-Driven CAUTI Prevention Protocol

REFERENCE #: 20-38X

SUBMISSION TYPE: New Project

ACTION: DETERMINATION OF EXEMPT STATUS

DECISION DATE: December 11, 2020

REVIEW CATEGORY: Exemption category # 2(i) and 4(ii)

Thank you for your submission of New Project materials for this project. The California State University, Los Angeles (Cal State LA) IRB has determined that this project is EXEMPT FROM IRB REVIEW according to federal regulations.

We will retain a copy of this correspondence within our records.

IF ANY CHANGES ARE MADE TO THE METHODS AND PROCEDURES DESCRIBED IN THIS PROTOCOL, YOU MUST SUBMIT A MODIFICATION APPLICATION SO THAT THE PROJECT MAY BE RE-EVALUATED FOR EXEMPTION FROM IRB REVIEW.

For any inquiries about this project, please use the Send Project Mail option on IRBNet to contact Claire Bakewell. **It allows us to keep all correspondence related to this project in one place, rather than scattered between IRBNet and emails.**

This letter has been electronically signed in accordance with all applicable regulations, and a copy is retained within California State University, Los Angeles (Cal State LA) IRB's records.

APPENDIX D

Nurses' Survey Informational Letter

EXEMPT INFORMATIONAL COVER

Nurses' Adherence to a CAUTI Prevention Protocol

To Project Participant:

You are invited to take part in a research project conducted by Odette Njecheu Tomta, a Doctor of Nursing Practice student at California State University, Los Angeles. In this study we hope to learn more about nurses' adherence to the CAUTI prevention protocol. You were selected to voluntarily participate in this evidence-based improvement project because you are part of the healthcare team. As a registered nurse, you are involved in direct care of patients with indwelling urinary catheters. We hope that our project will lead to a decrease in the inadequate utilization of indwelling urinary catheters, catheter days, and CAUTIs events. This project will take place over 2 months and will involve the Infection Preventionist, charge nurses, frontline registered nurses and CAUTI Prevention Champions. **Participants must be 18 years or older to participate. The project is under the supervision of Dr. Glenn Raup.**

I kindly request that you complete this 10-questions survey that will take approximately 5 to 10 minutes. The purpose of this survey is to identify nurses' perceptions of barriers to implement the nurse-driven CAUTI prevention protocol (CPP). Data obtained will be used to identify barriers to adherence to the CPP and to propose corrective measures. The results will be used to inform the development of interventions to increase bedside nurses' use of the CPP. There will be no financial compensation for participation.

There is minimal risk of potential loss of confidentiality. This risk is minimized by keeping **all surveys anonymous and by not having any identifying information on the surveys.** We will not be requesting nor collecting any identifying information, instead, surveys will be numbered. Participants may refuse to respond to any without penalty. All information gathered will remain confidential and be given out only with your permission or as required by law. If you choose to participate, we will protect your confidentiality. All surveys will be kept in a locked office and all electronic data will be stored in a secured device and will require a secure password for retrieval. Files will be kept in the Infection Prevention Service's office, although anonymous data files may be used at the student's home during the project period. Files will be kept for three years after the study is completed as required by the law, then data will be destroyed.

By completing the survey, you indicate that you have read this form and consent to voluntarily participate in the project. If you choose not to take part, there will be no penalty or loss of benefits to which you are entitled. If you agree to take part, you are free to withdraw from it at any time.

If you have any questions about this research at any time, please call Odette Njecheu Tomta at 818 398 0950 or email me at otomta27@gmail.com. You might also contact the project's Team Lead.

Team Lead: Glenn Raup, RN, PhD, MBA, MSN, CEN
714-771-8000 x12490
Glenn.Raup@stjoe.org
California State University, Fullerton

Respectfully,
Odette Njecheu Tomta, CNL, MSN, MS, RN, CMSRN, PHN

THIS PROJECT HAS BEEN DETERMINED TO BE EXEMPT FROM REVIEW AND APPROVAL BY THE CALIFORNIA STATE UNIVERSITY, LOS ANGELES INSTITUTIONAL REVIEW BOARD FOR THE PROTECTION OF HUMAN SUBJECTS IN RESEARCH.

Effective January 2018

APPENDIX E

Daily Rounding Checklist

Page __ to __

Audit Completed By: _____

Date: _____

Unit: _____

GLENDALE MEMORIAL HOSPITAL AND MEDICAL CENTER

Catheter Associated Urinary Tract Prevention **Rounding Checklist**

<p>Regular monitoring with feedback to staff can maintain or improve adherence to indwelling urinary catheter maintenance practices. Use this tool to identify gaps and opportunities for improvement. Monitoring may be performed in any type of patient care location where indwelling urinary catheters are used.</p> <p>Instructions: Use this tool to observe indwelling urinary catheters. Observe each maintenance practice and check a box if adherent (Yes or No). Check a box for each practice observed. In the column on the right, record the total number of "Yes" for adherent practices observed and the total number of observations ("Yes" + "No"). Calculate the adherence percentage in the last row. Please use another sheet if reviewing more than 4 Foley catheters.</p>							
Urinary Catheter Care Practices		Indwelling Urinary Catheter # 1	Indwelling Urinary Catheter # 2	Indwelling Urinary Catheter # 3	Indwelling Urinary Catheter # 4	Adherence by Task	
						# Yes	# Observed
Item 1	The indwelling urinary catheter used for an appropriate indication (see page 2)?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		
Item 2	Necessity for continuing the indwelling urinary catheter assessed?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		
Item 3	Seal between the catheter and collecting tubing intact?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		
Item 4	Catheter tubing unobstructed and not twisted, kinked, or looped?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		
Item 5	Urine collection bag below the level of the bladder?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		
Item 6	Catheter secured to the patient?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		
Item 7	Catheter not touching the floor?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		
Item 8	Catheter bag no more than 2/3 full?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		
Item 9	Daily perineal care completed?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		
Item 10	Patient &/or family provided with education handout within 24 hours of insertion?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		
Insertion Date & Time		Removal Date & Time					
# of Correct Practices Observed ("#Yes"): _____		Total # Indwelling Urinary Catheter Observations ("# Observed"): _____			Adherence _____ % (Total "# Yes" ÷ Total "# Observed") x 100		
<p><i>If practice could not be observed (i.e. cell is blank), do not count in total # Observed.</i></p> <p>All 4 Core Elements (*) are in place for all indwelling urinary catheters observed:</p> <p style="text-align: center;"><input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No</p>							

Adapted in part from the California Department of Public Health (CDPH)'s Indwelling Urinary Catheter Maintenance Practices Adherence Monitoring Tool, version 2016.10.13.

1

Page __ to __

<p>Appropriate Indications for Indwelling Urinary Catheter</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Acute urinary retention (i.e., sudden and painful inability to urinate) or bladder outlet obstruction <input type="checkbox"/> Critically ill and need for accurate measurements of I&O (i.e., hourly monitoring in ICU, thermodynamically unstable) <input type="checkbox"/> Prolonged immobilization (potentially unstable thoracic or lumbar spine, multiple traumatic injuries such as pelvic fractures, chemically paralyzed or sedated) <input type="checkbox"/> To assist in healing open sacral (Stage III or above) or perineal wound in the incontinent patient <input type="checkbox"/> To improve comfort for end-of-life care if needed <input type="checkbox"/> Selected surgical procedures (i.e., genitourinary tract surgery, colorectal surgery, operative patients with urinary incontinence) <input type="checkbox"/> Need for intraoperative monitoring of urinary output during surgery or large volumes of fluid or diuretics anticipated <input type="checkbox"/> Physician documented reason indwelling catheter is in place greater than 7 postoperative days <input type="checkbox"/> Gross hematuria requiring continuous bladder irrigation <input type="checkbox"/> Inserted by a urologist or patient under the care of a urologist
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APPENDIX F

Chart Review Checklist

Page __ of __

Audit Completed By: _____
Date: _____
Unit: _____

GLENDALE MEMORIAL HOSPITAL AND MEDICAL CENTER

Catheter Associated Urinary Tract Prevention Chart Review Checklist

Regular monitoring with feedback to staff can maintain or improve adherence to indwelling urinary catheter maintenance practices. Use this tool to identify gaps and for improvement. Monitoring may be performed in any type of patient care location where indwelling urinary catheters are used.

Instructions: Use this tool to review indwelling urinary catheters documentation in the EMR. Review each maintenance practice documentation in the EMR and check a box if adherent (Yes or No). Check a box for each practice documented. In the column on the right, record the total number of "Yes" for adherent practices documented and the total number of items documented ("Yes" + "No"). Calculate the adherence percentage in the last row. **Please use another sheet if reviewing more than 4 Foley catheters.**

Urinary Catheter Care Practices		Indwelling Urinary Catheter # ____	Indwelling Urinary Catheter # ____	Indwelling Urinary Catheter # ____	Indwelling Urinary Catheter # ____	Adherence by Task	
						# Yes	# Observed
Item 1	Indwelling urinary catheter insertion/start documented (Started in MediTech)?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		
Item 2	Indwelling urinary catheter used for an appropriate indication (see page 2)?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		
Item 3	Necessity for continuing the indwelling urinary catheter documented (see page 2)?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		
Item 4	Daily perineal care documented?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		
Item 5	Urine assessment documented? (output and character)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		
Item 6	Urinary catheter assessment documented? (type & size)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		
Item 7	Patient &/or family education documented?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		
Insertion Date & Time _____		Removal Date & Time _____					
# of Correct Practices Observed ("#Yes"): _____		Total # Indwelling Urinary Catheter Observations ("# Observed"): _____		Adherence _____% (Total "# Yes" ÷ Total "# Observed") x 100			
<i>If practice could not be observed (i.e. cell is blank), do not count in total # Observed.</i> All Elements are in place for all indwelling urinary catheters observed: <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No							

Adapted in part from the California Department of Public Health (CDPH)'s Indwelling Urinary Catheter Maintenance Practices Adherence Monitoring Tool, version 2016.10.13.

Page __ of __

Appropriate Indications for Indwelling Urinary Catheter
<input type="checkbox"/> Acute urinary retention (i.e., sudden and painful inability to urinate) or bladder outlet obstruction
<input type="checkbox"/> Critically ill and need for accurate measurements of I&O (i.e., hourly monitoring in ICU, thermodynamically unstable)
<input type="checkbox"/> Prolonged immobilization (potentially unstable thoracic or lumbar spine, multiple traumatic injuries such as pelvic fractures, chemically paralyzed or sedated)
<input type="checkbox"/> To assist in healing open sacral (Stage III or above) or perineal wound in the incontinent patient
<input type="checkbox"/> To improve comfort for end-of-life care if needed
<input type="checkbox"/> Selected surgical procedures (i.e., genitourinary tract surgery, colorectal surgery, operative patients with urinary incontinence)
<input type="checkbox"/> Need for intraoperative monitoring of urinary output during surgery or large volumes of fluid or diuretics anticipated
<input type="checkbox"/> Physician documented reason indwelling catheter is in place greater than 2 postoperative days
<input type="checkbox"/> Gross hematuria requiring continuous bladder irrigation
<input type="checkbox"/> Inserted by a urologist or patient under the care of a urologist

APPENDIX G

Risks and Indications for Foley Catheter Poster

REMOVE IT!

Urinary Catheters Increase...

- Length of Stay
- Cost
- Likelihood of Infection
- Patient Discomfort
- Antibiotic Use

...and patients with urinary catheters tend to stay in bed, increasing risk of skin breakdown, deep-vein thrombosis, weakness and delirium.

Urinary Catheters Are Indicated for...

- Acute urinary retention or obstruction
- Perioperative use in selected surgeries
- Assistance of healing of severe perineal and sacral wounds in incontinent patients
- Hospice, comfort care, or palliative care
- Required strict immobilization for trauma or surgery
- Accurate measurement of urinary output in critically ill patients (intensive care)

Catheters Are NOT Indicated for...

- Routine urine output monitoring outside the ICU
- Incontinence
- Prolonged postoperative use
- Morbid obesity
- Immobility
- Confusion or dementia
- Patient request

AHRQ
Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality
Advancing Excellence in Health Care • www.ahrq.gov

AHRQ Pub No. 15-0073-2-EF
September 2015

Toolkit for reducing catheter-associated urinary tract Infections in hospital units: implementation (AHRQ, 2015).

APPENDIX H

EB CAUTI Prevention Practices/Strategies Poster

Toolkit for reducing catheter-associated urinary tract Infections in hospital units: implementation (AHRQ, 2015).

APPENDIX I

Risks and Alternatives for Foley Catheter Poster

Stop catheter-associated urinary tract infections (CAUTI) in critically ill patients.

1. RAISE AWARENESS AND UNDERSTAND THE RISKS OF INDWELLING URINARY CATHETERS

Possible misconceptions:

What the science & evidence show:

CAUTI is a serious patient safety issue.¹

- Complications associated with CAUTI result in increased length of stay, patient discomfort, excess health care costs, and even death.
- It's about more than just the Foley. Unnecessary catheterization puts patients at risk for urinary tract infections and may cause other complications such as multidrug-resistant organisms, additional antibiotics leading to increased risk of *Clostridium difficile* infection, immobility (Foley is considered a "one-point restraint"), hospital-acquired pressure ulcers, falls, and venous thromboembolism.^{2,3}
- Not all critically ill, immobile patients need Foley catheters.
- All team members—from frontline staff to leaders—have a responsibility to help prevent CAUTI.
- CAUTI prevention is also tied to the "bottom line" with potential financial implications associated with Centers for Medicare & Medicaid Services and healthcare-acquired conditions, value based purchasing, and population health.
- CAUTI outcome measures are used to assess performance.

2. CONSIDER ALTERNATIVES FOR MEASURING FLUID INTAKE AND OUTPUT

3. RETHINK THE "CULTURE OF CULTURING" URINE

Reflex pan culturing may lead to *C. difficile* infection.

Asymptomatic bacteriuria + exposure to unnecessary antibiotics

possible *C. difficile* infection

If a patient develops a new fever, "...(> 38.3 C), it is a reasonable trigger for a clinical assessment but not necessarily a laboratory or radiologic evaluation for infection."⁴

Don't assume an ICU patient's fever is due to a urinary tract infection...

...Other causes could include:⁴

- Respiratory tract infection
- Gastrointestinal infection
- Bloodstream infection
- Neurological pathology that may result in altered thermoregulation

"Critical care units could reduce the cost of fever evaluations by eliminating automatic laboratory and radiologic tests for patients with new temperature elevation (level 2). Instead, these tests should be ordered based on clinical assessment."⁴

4. TACKLE CAUTI

1. Pause and verify that the patient has an approved indication before inserting catheter.
2. Involve a second person during insertion to facilitate aseptic technique.
3. Evaluate continued need daily.
4. Empower nursing staff to discontinue catheter use as soon as possible.

Make a difference. Change the culture. Visit www.ahrq.gov/CAUTItools for more information.

1. Bell L. AACN Practice Alert: Catheter-Associated Urinary Tract Infections. November 2011.
2. Saint S, Savel RH, Matthey MA. Enhancing the Safety of Critically Ill Patients by Reducing Urinary and Central Venous Catheter-related Infections. *Am J Resp Crit Care Med.* 2002;165:1475-9. PMID: 12045119.
3. Fakih MG, Krein SL, Edson B, et al. Engaging health care workers to prevent catheter-associated urinary tract infection and avert patient harm. *Am J Infect Control.* 2014 Oct;42(10 Suppl):S223-9. PMID: 25239714.
4. O'Grady NP, Barie PS, Bartlett JG, et al. Guidelines for evaluation of new fever in critically ill adult patients: 2008 update from the American College of Critical Care Medicine and the Infectious Diseases Society of America. *Crit Care Med.* 2008 Apr; 36(4):1330-1349. PMID: 18379262.

AHRQ Safety Program for Reducing CAUTI in Hospitals

AHRQ Pub No. 15-0073-2-EF
September 2015

Toolkit for reducing catheter-associated urinary tract Infections in hospital units: implementation (AHRQ, 2015).

APPENDIX J

SWOT Analysis

S	W	O	T
<p>Strengths</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Availability of a nurse-driven CAUTI prevention protocol/guideline - Availability of resources (alternatives for IUC, bladder scan, etc.) - Routine daily multi-disciplinary rounding (opportunity to assess IUCs necessity) - Highly educated & experienced nursing staff - IUC insertion criteria included in the EMR physician's order bundle - Existing continued education for staff nurses - Unit leadership support of evidence-based practice 	<p>Weaknesses</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increased workload due to Covid-19 surge - Limited nursing staff engagement - Poor physician/nurse communication & handoff on IUC necessity - Knowledge deficit on IUC risks & CAUTI prevention protocol - Lack of accountability for appropriate and safe practice (No daily physician's review of IUCs indications/orders) - Lack of unit-level CAUTI prevention physician champions - Lack of periodic physicians' education on CAUTI prevention - Lack of standardized patient/family education tool - No nurse-driven IUC removal protocol/algorithm 	<p>Opportunities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Strong nursing unit-based council dedicated to patient safety - Hospital leadership supportive of change initiatives - Strong education department - Increase in revenues due to decreased CAUTI cases/non reimbursement of CAUTI care - Improved patient outcome (decreased infection, morbidity & mortality) - Increased patient and staff satisfaction 	<p>Threats</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - High costs of updating the electronic medical record to include more detailed entries on IUCs - Staff resistance to EB practice changes - Covid-19 pandemic (increased patients' acuity & patient/nurse ratio & inadequate staffing) - Lack of continuous monitoring & audits - Patient/family requests/needs

APPENDIX K

Nurses' Survey

Nurses' Adherence to a CAUTI Prevention Protocol

Survey # _____

Please answer the following questions on a 5-point scale:

1 = Strongly disagree; 2 = Disagree; 3 = Neither agree nor disagree; 4 = Agree; 5 = Strongly agree.

- 1) The hospital's current catheter associated urinary tract infection protocol is easy for nurses to utilize. 1 2 3 4 5
- 2) I was adequately educated on the hospital's current catheter associated urinary tract infection protocol. 1 2 3 4 5
- 3) Physicians do not know the proper indications for Foley catheter use per the protocol
1 2 3 4 5
- 4) Physicians do not timely order removal of the foley catheter
1 2 3 4 5
- 5) During handoff indwelling urinary catheters are routinely addressed
1 2 3 4 5

Please check all that applies to the following questions to the best of your knowledge

6) What are the barriers to appropriate Foley catheter use?

- Patient and family requests for indwelling catheters
- Concerns or prioritization relative to other patient safety issues (Falls, incontinence dermatitis...)
- Catheter insertion practices and customs in the ICU
- Lack of proper physicians' education on the protocol
- Lack of proper frontline nurses' education on the protocol
- Limited availability of Foley catheter alternatives
- Lack/limited knowledge of the protocol
- Other _____

7) What are some barriers to aseptic Foley catheter insertion?

- Lack of proper training on the protocol

- Lack of knowledge of the protocol
- Lack of skills
- Lack of manpower (lack of assisting staff during the insertion process)
- Inconvenient or inconsistent location of hand cleaning gel/solution
- Lack of space for sterile field set up
- Lack of adequate supplies
- Lack of awareness of consequences of aseptic insertion violation

- Foley catheter insertion is a task rather than an evidence-based practice
- Work environment constraints (please give examples) _____
- Other _____

8) What are some barriers to evidence-based (EB) Foley catheter appropriate maintenance?

- Limited EB knowledge/kills of foley catheter maintenance
- Lack of training on EB Foley catheter maintenance
- Lack of time
- Uncleared/difficult protocol/guidelines
- Inadequate staffing
- Heavy nursing workload
- Lack of supplies
- Catheterized patients/family not educated on FC maintenance and infection prevention behaviors
- Lack of a standardized patient/family education tool for patient/family education
- Other _____

9) What are some barriers to timely Foley catheter removal?

- Lack of timely physician orders for removal
- Heavy nursing workload (i.e. spending more time cleaning patients, charting...)
- Physicians not routinely reviewing catheter necessity during rounds
- Catheters going unnoticed or hidden under clothing
- Little or no discussion of catheters among clinicians
- Catheter data are hard to find, not accurate, or not available
- Catheter removal not considered a priority
- Confusion exists about who has authority to remove catheters
- There is a lack of agreement on and awareness of standard protocols, and indications for removal
- Communication barriers among clinicians create challenges.
- Other _____

10) What are some barriers to proper documentation required by the CAUTI prevention protocol?

- Workload (concerns of spending more time charting)
- Lack of computer skills

- Documentation prompts not available on the worklist
 Lack of time
 Lack of adequate staffing
 Work environment constraints (please give examples) _____
 Other _____

Demographics

1. What is your gender? a. Male b. Female
2. What is your highest level of education achieved?
 a. Associate Degree b. Bachelor c. Master d. Doctorate
3. What is your age? a. 18-25 b. 26-35 c. 36-50 d. Over 50
4. What certifications do you hold? _____
5. What licenses do you hold? _____
6. How long have you been working at GMHMC (number of years)? _____
7. How long have you been working in the ICU (number of years)? _____

NB: After completion, please drop your survey in the Infection Prevention office locked drop box located on the 1st floor, room 109.

THIS PROJECT HAS BEEN DETERMINED TO BE EXEMPT FROM REVIEW AND APPROVAL BY THE CALIFORNIA STATE UNIVERSITY, LOS ANGELES INSTITUTIONAL REVIEW BOARD FOR THE PROTECTION OF HUMAN SUBJECTS IN RESEARCH.

APPENDIX L

CAUTI Education for Patients

Patient/Family Standardized CAUTI Prevention Education Handout

CAUTI Education for Patients

FAQs

(frequently asked questions)

about

“Catheter-Associated Urinary Tract Infection”

What is “catheter-associated urinary tract infection”?

A urinary tract infection (also called “UTI”) is an infection in the urinary system, which includes the bladder (which stores the urine) and the kidneys (which filter the blood to make urine). Germs (for example, bacteria or yeasts) do not normally live in these areas; but if germs are introduced, an infection can occur.

If you have a urinary catheter, germs can travel along the catheter and cause an infection in your bladder or your kidney; in that case it is called a catheter-associated urinary tract infection (or “CA-UTI”).

What is a urinary catheter?

A urinary catheter is a thin tube placed in the bladder to drain urine. Urine drains through the tube into a bag that collects the urine. A urinary catheter may be used:

- If you are not able to urinate on your own
- To measure the amount of urine that you make, for example, during intensive care
- During and after some types of surgery
- During some tests of the kidneys and bladder

People with urinary catheters have a much higher chance of getting a urinary tract infection than people who don’t have a catheter.

How do I get a catheter-associated urinary tract infection (CA-UTI)?

If germs enter the urinary tract, they may cause an infection. Many of the germs that cause a catheter-associated urinary tract infection are common germs found in your intestines that do not usually cause an infection there. Germs can enter the urinary tract when the catheter is being put in or while the catheter remains in the bladder.

What are the symptoms of a urinary tract infection?

Some of the common symptoms of a urinary tract infection are:

- Burning or pain in the lower abdomen (that is, below the stomach)
- Fever
- Bloody urine may be a sign of infection, but is also caused by other problems
- Burning during urination or an increase in the frequency of urination after the catheter is removed.

Sometimes people with catheter-associated urinary tract infections do not have these symptoms of infection.

Can catheter-associated urinary tract infections be treated?

Yes, most catheter-associated urinary tract infections can be treated with antibiotics and removal or change of the catheter. Your doctor will determine which antibiotic is best for you.

What are some of the things that hospitals are doing to prevent catheter-associated urinary tract infections?

To prevent urinary tract infections, doctors and nurses take the following actions:

Catheter insertion

- Catheters are put in only when necessary and they are removed as soon as possible.
- Only properly trained persons insert catheters using sterile (“clean”) technique.
- The skin in the area where the catheter will be inserted is cleaned before inserting the catheter.
- Other methods to drain the urine are sometimes used, such as
- External catheters in men (these look like condoms and are placed over the penis rather than into the penis)
- Putting a temporary catheter in to drain the urine and removing it right away. This is called intermittent urethral catheterization.

Catheter care

- Healthcare providers clean their hands by washing them with soap and water or using an alcohol-based hand rub before and after touching your catheter.

If you do not see your providers clean their hands, please ask them to do so.

- Avoid disconnecting the catheter and drain tube. This helps to prevent germs from getting into the catheter tube.
- The catheter is secured to the leg to prevent pulling on the catheter.
- Avoid twisting or kinking the catheter.
- Keep the bag lower than the bladder to prevent urine from backflowing to the bladder.
- Empty the bag regularly. The drainage spout should not touch anything while emptying the bag.

What can I do to help prevent catheter-associated urinary tract infections if I have a catheter?

- Always clean your hands before and after doing catheter care.
- Always keep your urine bag below the level of your bladder.
- Do not tug or pull on the tubing.
- Do not twist or kink the catheter tubing.
- Ask your healthcare provider each day if you still need the catheter.

What do I need to do when I go home from the hospital?

- If you will be going home with a catheter, your doctor or nurse should explain everything you need to know about taking care of the catheter. Make sure you understand how to care for it before you leave the hospital.
- If you develop any of the symptoms of a urinary tract infection, such as burning or pain in the lower abdomen, fever, or an increase in the frequency of urination, contact your doctor or nurse immediately.
- Before you go home, make sure you know who to contact if you have questions or problems after you get home.

If you have questions, please ask your doctor or nurse.

Co-sponsored by:

Urinary tract infection (catheter-associated urinary tract infection [CAUTI] and non-catheter-associated urinary tract infection (UTI]) and other urinary system infection [USI]) (CDC, 2019).

APPENDIX M

Project Facility's Approval Letter

Dignity Health
Glendale Memorial Hospital and
Health Center

INSTITUTION APPROVAL LETTER

November 17, 2020

This letter is to show that I, Ron Yolo, as the Chief Nursing Executive Officer at Glendale Memorial Hospital and Health Center, give permission to Odette Njecheu Tomta to conduct the evidence-based improvement project titled "Nurses' Adherence to a Catheter-Associated Urinary Tract Infections Protocol" in the intensive care unit or any other unit(s).

Odette will work in conjunction with the Infection Prevention Services, Education Department and other stakeholders as necessary. Upon obtaining all necessary clearances from the Nursing Research Council, and /or the International Research Board (IRB) approval, the above-named Project Lead is allowed to:

- 1) Collect the unit/project site aggregate data on Foley catheter insertion, maintenance, and removal, Foley catheter utilization rates, Foley catheter days, CAUTI events, CAUTI rates, and nurses' adherence to the CAUTI prevention protocol.
- 2) Conduct necessary interactions, collaborate, and communicate with IT services, Quality Improvement, Infection Prevention Services, Education Department, ICU leaders, and nursing staff.
- 3) Distribute a survey to nursing staff.
- 4) Conduct a SWOT analysis.

The Project Lead is responsible to ensuring that all activities related to conducting the project are in compliance with the policies that govern practice, HIPAA, research and research related regulations at Glendale Memorial Hospital and Health Center and its covered entities.

If you have any questions or concerns, please do not hesitate to contact me.

Sincerely,

Ron Yolo, MSN, MBA, RN
Chief Nursing Officer
Glendale Memorial Hospital & Health Center
ron.yolo@dignityhealth.org
818.502.2203